

D2.3 Databases and ontology definition

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MARINA
**Marine Knowledge Sharing Platform for Federating
Responsible Research and Innovation Communities**

Grant Agreement No. 710566

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The Deliverable D2.3 is an evolution of the Deliverable D2.2 that will take into account the concepts emerging from the documentation produced by the second round of MML workshops and the spillover and policy mobilization activities and defines the final version of the ontology for the MARINA WKSP and the wiki platform. The revised ontology of the deliverable D2.3 will be defined in Month 30 (October 2018). The document is in progress and will be updated monthly.

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Deliverable	Databases and ontology definition
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Abstract	Deliverable D2.3 builds a database of stakeholders and an ontology starting from the taxonomy defined in D2.1 taking into account the information selected in MS1 and the outcome of the second round of local MML workshops. The Deliverable D2.3 is an evolution of the Deliverable D2.2 to include the concepts and relationships emerged during the second round of local MML workshops (focused on new hot topics and themes), the spillover and policy mobilization activities. The ontology will be used to classify and relate the information in the MARINA Web Knowledge Sharing Platform (WKSP) for supporting the community members to easily search, find and extract the information of interest.
Title and number of connected deliverables	Criteria for identifying, collecting, analysing and extracting information from sources and taxonomy D2.1. Database and Ontology Definition D2.2 Comprehensive Report on Local MML workshops D3.2 Comprehensive Report on Local MML workshops D3.3
Explain Deliverable Dependency/ Connection	This deliverable updates the deliverable D2.2, uses the outcomes of the D2.1 "Criteria for identifying, collecting and extracting information from sources and taxonomy", D3.2 "Comprehensive Report on Local MML workshops" D3.3 "Comprehensive Report on Local MML workshops (second round)" to identify

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	relevant concepts to include in the ontology.
Title of connected external documents	For clarity's sake, the links are cited contextually into the report

Reference of the document and the link (if available)	
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1. Objective and Purpose

One of the main aims of the MARINA project is to federate RRI communities that deal with marine issues and challenges into the MARINA Community. This aim is ambitious because community members have diverse backgrounds and may use the same term with a slightly different meaning, which depends on the members' education, field of work, experience etc. Thus, in order to federate diverse actors into one community, it is necessary to “speak the same language”. Hence, it is necessary for the members of the MARINA Community to define and accept a “common vocabulary” with a set of terms that are used within marine sciences and RRI. This common vocabulary must be structured by a central team of the MARINA Project. Once the vocabulary is managed, it is called a “controlled vocabulary¹”. This means that a set of procedures are defined for defining terms, adding terms, modifying terms and even deprecating terms. In the case of the MARINA Project, it is necessary to go a step further from a simple glossary and create a Relational Controlled Vocabulary by defining an ‘ontology’.

The MARINA Project has already defined a ‘taxonomy’, which means that important terms are placed in a classified structure (D2.1). Furthermore, the milestone MS1 has defined databases of existing projects, tools and information sources. Deliverable 2.2 went a step further building a database of stakeholders and an ontology starting from the taxonomy defined in D2.1 taking into account the information selected in MS1. The ontology has been built by using the inputs from MS1, the Deliverable D2.1 and a desk analysis of existing ontologies, thesauri and terminological databases. The use of an ontology allows a user that searches an information in the MARINA Web Knowledge Sharing Platform (WKSP) (WP4) to obtain as a result not only the concepts containing the search keyword but also all semantically related concepts. By using a taxonomy, instead of an ontology, only concepts related by hierarchical relationships (defined by superclass/subclass relations) and synonymy could be retrieved, while using an ontology also concepts related by more specific semantic relationships (such as InstanceOf, Concerns, isPartOf, isInfluencedBy, etc.) can be retrieved (see Section 3.2 for a complete list of semantic relationships considered in the MARINA ontology). This allows a deeper and more careful information extraction process.

Therefore, ontology will be used to classify and relate the information in the MARINA Web Knowledge Sharing Platform (WKSP) (WP4) for supporting the community members to easily search, find and extract the information of interest. In fact, through the MARINA Web Knowledge Sharing Platform, the MARINA Community may share information (documents, results, experiences, pictures, videos). The ontology contains the concepts that categorise these contents of the MARINA WKSP, and by using this categorization the MARINA WKSP activates the possibility of having an extraction and retrieval based on these concepts and their relationships added to the already available “full text search” based on keywords, titles and authors. The present deliverable uses and enriches well-established definitions already developed in other ontologies and thesauri defined in EU-funded research projects, in the Coastal Wiki2, in research journals and in widely used statistical glossaries. The Deliverable D2.3 is an evolution of the Deliverable D2.2 and takes into account the concepts emerged by the second round of local MML workshops and

¹What is a Controlled Vocabulary? <https://marinemetadata.org/guides/vocabs/vocdef> (Last accessed 2/1/2017)

² http://www.coastalwiki.org/wiki/Main_Page

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produces the ontology for the MARINA WKSP and the wiki platform. The revised ontology of the deliverable D2.3 will be defined in Month 30 (October 2018).

Two different tasks give contributions to the D.2.3:

- Task T2.1: Info process definition that defines the ontology
- Task T2.3: Creation of a stakeholders database, that specifies the structure of the stakeholders database and a first list of relevant stakeholders.

2. Stakeholders Database: key concepts

Task 2.3, based on the information collected in Task 2.2 and the type of actors identified, specifies the database of stakeholders. The Stakeholders are described in the database with the information shown below in Table 1.

Table 1: Stakeholder database (Task 2.3)

	Information	Predefined values
1.	Name of Stakeholder's Organisation (if part of an organisation)	
2.	Organisation type	Governmental organisation Research Organisation Higher Education Other public organisation Civil Society Organisation NGOs Citizen Industry - according to Eurostat categories Other
3.	Website	
4.	Name of Stakeholder	
5.	Email	
6.	Postal address	
7.	Country	
8.	Language (first/second/third)	
9.	Domain of activity	Local/ National/ EU/ Global
10.	Link to RRI principles (if relevant)	Public Engagement Gender Equality Science literacy and scientific education Open access Ethics

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	Governance
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The database of Stakeholders is part of the overall MARINA database.

3. Ontology definition

This section illustrates the ontology based on the taxonomy defined in the deliverable D2.1. The ontology provides explicit formal specifications of the terms in the domain and relations among them for categorising the information of the MARINA WKSP platform. As introduced before the ontology is finalised for extracting and retrieving the information of interest for the user supporting queries and navigation on the platform, for this reason this deliverable introduces the main methods for information extraction and retrieval that will be analysed for choosing the methods used by the MARINA WKSP platform.

3.1 Related works on ontology-based methods for information extraction

Since the ontology can be considered as background knowledge for representing the concepts and the relationship in specialized domains, it can be viewed as “the solution for searching relevant information from huge repository of unstructured web data”³. In fact, information extraction process employs ontologies as means to formally describe the domain knowledge exploited by systems for their operations. Ontology allows modelling knowledge about domain entities, but also conceptual hierarchies, properties and relations in order to discover implicit information.

Several works^{3,4,5,6,7} applied ontology-based methods in order to extract information from unstructured data. When considering the marine domain, an example of ontology is MarineTLO⁸ that provides consistent abstractions or specifications of concepts included in all data models of marine data sources and provide the necessary properties to make this distributed knowledge base a coherent source of facts relating observational data with the respective spatiotemporal context and categorical domain knowledge. A further example has been defined by the NETMAR

³ G. A. Patel, N. Madia, *A Survey: Ontology Based Information Retrieval For Sentiment Analysis*, International Journal of Scientific Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (IJSRSET), Volume 2 Issue 2, pp.460-465, March-April 2016.

⁴ U. Shah, J. Mayfield: *Information Retrieval on the Semantic Web*, In Proceedings of the ACM CIKM International Conference on Information Management, Nov 2002.

⁵ S. Luke, L. Spector, D. Rager and J. Hendler: *An Introduction to Ontology*, In Proceedings of the First International Conference on Autonomous Agents, 1997.

⁶ B. Lee, J. Lassila: *Ontologies in Semantic Web*, Scientific American, May 2001, pp 34-43. (PD: comment: T. B.-Lee and not B. Lee)

⁷ Thomas R. Gruber, *Toward principles for the design of ontologies used for knowledge sharing?*, In International Journal of Human-Computer Studies, Volume 43, Issues 5–6, 1995, Pages 907-928, ISSN 1071-5819, <https://doi.org/10.1006/ijhc.1995.1081>

⁸ MarineTLO: a top-level ontology for the marine domain. <http://www.ics.forth.gr/isl/MarineTLO/>.

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project that identified a number of ontologies, both specific to the marine domain as well as more generic resources that have been used as building blocks in a semantic infrastructure⁹.

Current Ontology-based information extraction systems were classified by Daya et al.¹⁰ according to the main information extraction methods employed:

- Linguistic rules represented by regular expressions. These systems specify regular expressions that capture certain types of information. Significant amount of information are extracted by specifying set of regular expressions that are often implemented by series of finite state automata. The regular expressions are used to define linguistic rules that are combined with the elements of the ontology (i.e. classes and properties) for information extraction¹¹. As example, ontoX¹² utilises the ontology as conceptualization of a domain of interest and formulates regular expressions to locate candidate values, that were relevant according to the considered ontology, and applies several heuristics to choose the most accurate values among them.
- Gazetteer lists. These systems apply finite-state automata similarly to the linguistic rules but differently from them these systems recognize individual words or phrases instead of patterns. The gazetteer lists, used by these systems, contain instances of the classes of the ontology. Saggion et al.¹³ propose a system that extracts and merges information from various sources (e.g. database, financial reports, news reports, company web sites) and for specific applications in financial risk management and internationalization. Information consists in concepts (e.g. person names, locations, organisation, dates), instances, and properties from documents in different formats (e.g. plain text, HTML, XML, RTF, and SGML) that are automatically annotated and transformed into tuples for ontology population.
- Classification techniques. These systems use different classification techniques (such as support vector machines (SVM), maximum entropy models, Hidden Markov Models, Conditional random field and decision trees) in order to extract information. The classification techniques are trained in order to identify the different components of the ontology, such as instances and properties values¹⁴. As example, Li and

⁹ Adam Leadbetter, Torill Hamre, Roy Lowry, Yassine Lassoued, Declan Dunne: Ontologies and ontology extension for marine environmental information systems. Proceedings of the Workshop Environmental Information Systems and Services-Infrastructures and Platforms, Edited by Arne J Berre, Dumitru Roman and Patrick Maue,(envip'2010), Bonn, Germany: CEUR Workshop Proceeding

¹⁰ D.C. Wimalasuriya, D. Dou: *Ontology-based information extraction: An introduction and a survey of current approaches*. Journal of Information Science Vol 36, Issue 3, pp. 306 – 323, June 2010.

¹¹ M. Vargas-Vera, E. Motta, J. Domingue, S.B. Shum and M. Lanzoni: *Knowledge extraction by using an ontology-based annotation tool*. In Proceedings of the Workshop on Knowledge Markup and Semantic Annotation, ACM, New York, 2001.

¹² B. Yildiz and S. Miksch: *ontoX - a method for ontology-driven information extraction*. In Proceedings of the 2007 international conference on Computational science and its applications, Vol. Part III. Springer-Verlag, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp 660-673, 2007.

¹³ H. Saggion, A. Funk, D. Maynard and K. Bontcheva: *Ontology-based information extraction for business intelligence*. In Proceedings of the 6th International and 2nd Asian Semantic Web Conference, Springer, Berlin, 2007.

¹⁴ F. Wu and D.S. Weld: *Autonomously semantifying wikipedia*. In Proceedings of the Sixteenth ACM Conference on Information and Knowledge Management, ACM, New York, 2007.

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Bontcheva¹⁵ propose an ontology-based information extraction system that uses a hierarchical classification learning algorithm for the semantic annotation that takes into account the relations between concepts.

- Construction of partial parse trees. These systems use semantically annotated parse tree for the text in order to extract information. The parse tree are built in order to represent the semantic content of the text in order to produce under-specified dependency structures¹⁶. Todirascu et al.¹⁷ provide a system that identifies domain-specific terms and concepts, using syntactic information and an existing domain ontology. In particular, this system uses partial syntactic structures to identify concept candidates and logical inferences available in Description Logics that is used as knowledge representation formalism.
- Analyzing HTML/XML tags. These systems use the tags of html or xml pages in order to extract certain types of information. As example, Buitelaar and Siegel¹⁸ propose an ontology-based information extraction system for automatic population of a knowledge base that can be used for domain specific question answering (in the example from HTML web pages). This system semantically extracts information (corpus of web pages) from heterogeneous sources (e.g. tabular structures, text and image captions from HTML tables) and stores it in a knowledge base, and uses the knowledge base to interpret and link newly extracted information with respect to already existing entities.
- Web-based search. These systems apply queries on web-based search engine. They semantically annotate web pages by using web-based search¹⁹. As example, Vargas-Vera and al.²⁰ propose an ontology-based mark-up system that allows to browse and mark-up relevant pieces of information. This system learns rules from examples available from the web and extracts the objects and relation between these objects in order to populate the ontology using linguistic rules and partial parse trees.

The methods that will be analysed in Task 4.2 to be candidate for implementing the ontological support for the MARINA WKSP are: Linguistic rules represented by regular expressions and Classification techniques.

By using the linguistic rules method, the MARINA ontology could be used as a knowledge base that represents the conceptualisation of the domain. The linguistic rules takes the user request and the MARINA ontology to determine what could be relevant and has to be extracted and retrieved from the MARINA platform.

¹⁵ Y. Li and K. Bontcheva: *Hierarchical, perceptron-like learning for ontology-based information extraction*. In Proceedings of the 16th international conference on World Wide Web (WWW '07). ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp. 777-786.

¹⁶ A. Maedche, G. Neumann and S. Staab: *Bootstrapping an ontology-based information extraction system*. In Intelligent Exploration of the Web, Physica-Verlag GmbH, Heidelberg, Germany, 2003.

¹⁷ A. Todirascu, L. Romary, D. Bekhouche: *Vulcain — An Ontology-Based Information Extraction System*. In Natural Language Processing and Information Systems. NLDB 2002. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 2553. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2002.

¹⁸ P. Buitelaar and M. Siegel: *Ontology-based information extraction with SOBA*. In Proceedings of the Fifth International Conference on Language Resources and Evaluation, European Language Resources Association, Genoa, Italy, 2006.

¹⁹ P. Cimiano, S. Handschuh and S. Staab: *Towards the self-annotating web*. In Proceedings of the 13th International Conference on World Wide Web, ACM, New York, 2004.

²⁰ M. Vargas-Vera, E. Motta, J. Domingue, S.B. Shum and M. Lanzoni: *Knowledge extraction by using an ontology-based annotation tool*. In Proceedings of the Workshop on Knowledge Markup and Semantic Annotation, ACM, New York, 2001.

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Ontology-based information extraction based on classification techniques may be applied to the MARINA WKSP for identifying and classifying information entities in user requests as instances of concepts in the MARINA ontology to be applied for supporting the extraction process of information by taking into account the relations (e.g. hierarchical relations) between the classes in the MARINA ontology.

3.2 Specifications of the terms and relations in the domain

The topics of interest for the community of MARINA are very large and are referred to different domains. For this reason the ontology is organised and stratified in eight main sections. This allows to improve the readability of ontology, but also its modularity and reusability. In particular, modularity implies the possibility of extracting and managing modules of the ontology relevant to a particular application scenario or developing them independently and integrating into a larger ontology. Reusability implies the possibility of modifying and adapting the ontology to different contexts. The reuse of the existing ontology can occur either while designing a new ontology or while developing new application domains. This stratified organization implies the ability to share, reuse and personalize the existing ontology since designing and maintaining the ontology is deemed to be a time-consuming and labor intensive task.

The sections were chosen to enable an intuitive classification and organisation of knowledge in the MARINA KSP as well as to take into account cross references among concepts. The eight sections are:

1. **Horizon 2020:** Policy programme for EU-funded Research and Innovation (RI) projects
2. **RRI Dimensions:** Responsible Research and Innovation keys as defined in https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_public_engagement/responsible-research-and-innovation-leaflet_en.pdf
3. **Marine Related Issues:** major empirical issues affecting maritime affairs in challenging ways derived from the EU Blue Growth Strategy²¹, that is part of the Integrated Maritime Policy²²,
4. **Growth sectors:** major growing sectors²³ derived and adjusted by the EU Blue Growth Strategy⁶
5. **Themes:** major multidimensional themes debated at international level partly derived from the European Environmental Agency's website²⁴
6. **Policy Framework:** a logical structure for organizing policy documentation to be used in the planning and development of the policies for an organization.
7. **EU Marine Regions:** acknowledged marine areas in the EU²⁵ on the basis of geographical and environmental criteria
8. **States:** autonomous political structure and government

²¹https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/policy/blue_growth

²²<https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/policy>

²³<https://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors>

²⁴<http://www.eea.europa.eu>

²⁵The EEA provides the following overview, the Greenland Sea not included: http://www.eea.europa.eu/about-us/countries-and-ionet/marine-regions/marine-regions-map/image_large

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Dimensions 3 to 5 warrant some clarification, as these at a first glance may seem to overlap. However, each dimension has a different origin and meaning. 'Issues' are basically *politically* defined issues; accordingly, the function of having 'issues' as part of the MARINA Ontology is to ensure a link to the EU policy level and the current policy context. 'Growth sectors' are basically well-established *economically* defined fields related to marine markets; consequently, the function of having 'sectors' as part of the MARINA Ontology is to ensure a link to well-established and promising marine sectors. Sectors are furthermore important due to the fact that the RRI approach of the EU is a combined policy and method approach for creating economic growth in a responsible way. 'Themes' are basically *environmental* themes; the function of having themes as part of the MARINA Ontology is to ensure that the sustainability aspect of RRI remains the core in the MARINA project. This is especially so in the marine field since the marine field in terms of both policy and economy is in general vital for the EU; however, in contrast to other fields, the marine field is particularly vulnerable to complex environmental damage, exploitation and threats.

The extensive table below (Table 2: MARINA WKSP Ontology specification) presents the definitions for the eight dimensions listed above. Apart from the document sources already explicitly mentioned in the list above, the definitions are based/adapted from existing knowledge and EU-agency positions²⁶:

- OECD Statistical Glossary
- Coastal Wiki
- Research Journals
- European Union official homepages
- EU-funded knowledge generating projects

Most definitions are direct quotations in order to ensure objectivity and accuracy; some have been reduced in order to accommodate user interaction and community building on the MARINA Knowledge Sharing Platform. References are provided in footnotes after each quote. In some instances, the MARINA consortium has supplemented with meaningful categories in case some are missing; in these cases this is explicitly stated. In terms of clarification of the definitions, the dimensions 7 to 8 are straightforward as these refer to established territorial and judicial definitions.

Table 2 describes the concepts used in the MARINA D2.3, the relationships among the concepts and the concepts definitions.

The relationships create a hierarchical taxonomy, a tree like structure that clearly shows how objects are related to each other. Typically a relation is a particular type (or property) that specifies in what sense the object is related to the other object in the ontology. In particular, the relationships between objects of the ontology specify how objects are related to other objects.

The relationships used in the Table 2 are:

²⁶All website references have been checked and accessed 13 December 2016.

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- **Superclass:** the relationship “C1→Superclass→C2” is used to state that C1 is a subclass of C2 and C1 inherits all the properties from the Superclass C2. All instances of C1 are also instances of C2. This property is transitive. This relationship is put in evidence in the Table 2 by indenting the concepts. However, because we assume multiple inheritance for the ontology concepts, the indentation highlights one Superclass relationship, the others are specified in the concept definition.
- **IsImplementedBy:** the relationship “C1→IsImplementedBy→C2” states that plans stated in the class C1 are actuated or used for acting by the class C2.
- **IsFundedBy:** the relationship “C1→IsFundedBy→C2” states that the item stated in the class C1 is funded by the funding source stated in the class C2.
- **IsInfluencedBy:** the relationship “C1→IsInfluencedBy→C2” states that the class C2 has the power to have effect on the class C1 modifying its characteristics and behaviour.
- **IsPartOf:** the relationship “C1→IsPartOf→C2” states that the class C1 is one of the basic structuring primitives of the class C2.
- **TheSameAs:** the relationship expresses equivalence. This relationship “C1→TheSameAs→C2” states that seemingly different individuals of C1 are actually the same of C2.
- **Overlaps:** the relationship “C1→ Overlaps→C2” states that the class C1 has some parts that are the same of the class C2.
- **IsFosteredBy:** the relationship “C1→IsFosteredBy→C2” states that the class C2 has effect on the class C1 empowering its characteristics and behaviour.
- **Concerns:** the relationship “C1→Concerns→C2” states that the class C1 is relevant for the characteristics of the class C2.
- **IsActuatedBy:** the relationship “C1→IsActuatedBy→C2” states that the objectives stated in the class C1 are obtained by the class C2.
- **InstanceOf:** the members of a class are known as instances of the class. The relationship “C1→ InstanceOf:→C2” states that the resource C1 is an instance of a class C2.

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Table 2: MARINA WKSP Ontology specification

Horizon 2020: Policy programme for EU-funded Research and Innovation (RI) projects		
Research Funding Program	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Financial instrument"	A research funding programme is an organisational setting which distributes public project funding for research on a regular and organised basis. ²⁷
Horizon 2020	<i>Superclass</i> : "Research Funding Program"	<p>Horizon 2020 is the organisational setting of funding programme for public project funding for research "implementing the <u>Innovation Union</u>, a <u>Europe 2020</u> flagship initiative aimed at securing Europe's global competitiveness.</p> <p>Seen as a means to drive economic growth and create jobs, Horizon 2020 has the political backing of Europe's leaders and the Members of the European Parliament. They agreed that research is an investment in our future and so put it at the heart of the EU's blueprint for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth and jobs.</p> <p>By coupling research and innovation, Horizon 2020 is helping to achieve this with its emphasis on excellent science, industrial leadership and tackling societal challenges. The goal is to ensure Europe produces world-class science, removes barriers to innovation and makes it easier for the public and private sectors to work together in delivering innovation.</p> <p>Horizon 2020 is open to everyone, with a simple structure that reduces red tape and time so participants can focus on what is really important. This approach makes sure new projects get off the ground quickly – and achieve results faster.</p> <p>The EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation will be complemented by further measures to complete and further develop the <u>European Research Area</u>. These measures will aim at breaking down barriers to create a genuine single market for knowledge, research and innovation."²⁸</p>
Horizon 2020 Societal challenges	<i>Superclass</i> : "Horizon 2020" <i>Overlaps</i> : "Science with and for Society" <i>Overlaps</i> : "Key Enabling Technologies"	<p>Horizon 2020 Societal challenges is the organisational setting of the H2020 funding programme for public project funding for research that "reflects the policy priorities of the Europe 2020 strategy and addresses major concerns shared by citizens in Europe and elsewhere.</p> <p>A challenge-based approach will bring together resources and knowledge across different fields, technologies and disciplines, including social sciences and the humanities. This will cover activities from research to market with a new focus on innovation-related activities, such as piloting, demonstration,</p>

²⁷ B.Lepori, P. van den Besselaar, M. Dinges, B. van der Meulen, B. Potì, E. Reale, S. Sliemersaeter and J. Theves: *Indicators for Comparative Analysis of Public Project Funding: Concepts, Implementation and Evaluation*, Research Evaluation, 16 (4), 243-255 2007b

²⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/what-horizon-2020>

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		<p>test-beds, and support for public procurement and market uptake. It will include establishing links with the activities of the European Innovation Partnerships (EIP).</p> <p>Funding will focus on the following challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health, demographic change and wellbeing; • Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the bioeconomy; • Secure, clean and efficient energy; • Smart, green and integrated transport; • Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials; • Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies; <p>Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens".²⁹</p>
Health, demographic change and wellbeing	<i>Superclass</i> : "Horizon 2020 Societal challenges"	<p>It is the organisational setting for public project funding for research that responds to the challenge of "better health for all. It aims to keep older people active and independent for longer and supports the development of new, safer and more effective interventions. R&I under Horizon 2020 also contributes to the sustainability of health and care systems".³⁰</p>
Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy	<i>Superclass</i> : "Horizon 2020 Societal challenges"	<p>It is the organisational setting for public project funding for research that responds to the challenge of "A transition towards an optimal and renewable use of biological resources and towards sustainable primary production and processing systems. These systems will need to produce more food, fibre and other bio-based products with minimised inputs, environmental impact and greenhouse gas emissions, and with enhanced ecosystem services, zero waste and adequate societal value.</p> <p>Agriculture, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture, together with the bio-based industries, are integral parts of the European economy and society. Relying on the use of limited natural resources, these sectors produce and process biological resources to satisfy the demand of consumers and a wide range of industries for food, feed, bio-energy and bio-based products. While they enhance Europe's self-reliance and provide jobs and business opportunities essential for rural, coastal and marine areas, these sectors are also facing significant challenges which require solutions based on research and innovation.</p> <p>Agriculture and forestry Agriculture and forestry have always had and maintain an important role for EU's society: they supply reliable, healthy and nutritious food as well as feed and non-food products for a wide range of industries,</p>

²⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/societal-challenges>

³⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/health-demographic-change-and-wellbeing>

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		<p>shape and take care of our landscapes, provide public goods, and keep the countryside alive by providing jobs. Research activities and policies will help to cope with the three main challenges these sectors are facing today: securing viable food production in face of a growing world food demand; ensuring sustainable management of natural resources and climate action; and finally to contribute to a balanced territorial development of the EU's rural areas and their communities.</p> <p>Agri-food sector for a safe and healthy diet Ensuring food security goes beyond securing a sufficient supply. It also requires social and economic access to safe and nutritious food. Food consumption has an impact on human health and the environment. The challenge is how to meet consumers' needs and preferences while minimising the related impact on health and the environment. Research and innovation will address food and feed security and safety, the competitiveness of the European agri-food industry and the sustainability of food production, processing and consumption. It will cover the whole food chain and related services from primary production to consumption.</p> <p>Aquatic living resources and marine research Oceans and seas represent over 70% of the earth's surface, and living aquatic resources can provide a significant contribution to food, energy and bio-based products. The objective is to sustainably manage and exploit aquatic living resources to maximise benefits from Europe's oceans, seas and inland waters. This includes optimising the sustainable contribution of fisheries and aquaculture to food security, boosting innovation through blue biotechnologies and fostering cross-cutting marine and maritime research to harness the potential of Europe's oceans, seas and coasts for jobs and growth.</p> <p>Bio-based industries The transition from fossil-based European industries towards low carbon, resource efficient and sustainable ones is a major challenge. It entails the transformation of conventional industrial processes and products into environmentally friendly bio-based ones, the development of integrated bio-refineries and the opening of new markets for bio-based products. Research and innovation will provide the means to reduce the Union's dependency on fossil resources and contribute to meeting its energy and climate change policy targets for 2020. Investments in research and innovation under this societal challenge will support Europe in contributing to food security, climate protection and sustainability. It will also enable Europe to take leadership in the concerned markets and will play a role in supporting the goals of the Common Agricultural Policy, the European Bioeconomy Strategy, and more broadly of the Europe 2020 strategy and its flagship initiatives</p>
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		'Innovation Union' and 'Resource-efficient Europe'. ³¹
Secure, clean and efficient energy	<i>Superclass</i> : "Horizon 2020 Societal challenges"	<p>It is the organisational setting for public project funding for research that responds to the challenge "to support the transition to a reliable, sustainable and competitive energy system. To make the transition to a competitive energy system, we need to overcome a number of challenges, such as increasingly scarce resources, growing energy needs and climate change.</p> <p>The Energy Challenge is structured around seven specific objectives and research areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reducing energy consumption and carbon footprint • Low-cost, low-carbon electricity supply • Alternative fuels and mobile energy sources • A single, smart European electricity grid • New knowledge and technologies • Robust decision making and public engagement • Market uptake of energy and ICT innovation. <p>A budget of €5 931 million has been allocated to non-nuclear energy research for the period 2014-2020. Out of this figure, more than €200 million is earmarked to support European Institute of Innovation and Technology activities, subject to a mid-term review".³²</p>
Smart, green and integrated transport	<i>Superclass</i> : "Horizon 2020 Societal challenges"	<p>It is the organisational setting for public project funding for research that responds to the challenge to "boost the competitiveness of the European transport industries and achieve a European transport system that is resource-efficient, climate-and-environmentally-friendly, safe and seamless for the benefit of all citizens, the economy and society".³³</p>
Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials	<i>Superclass</i> : "Horizon 2020 Societal challenges"	<p>It is the organisational setting for public project funding for research that responds to the challenge to "increase European competitiveness, raw materials security and improve wellbeing. At the same time they will assure environmental integrity, resilience and sustainability with the aim of keeping average global warming below 2° C and enabling ecosystems and society to adapt to climate change and other environmental changes. This Challenge funds research and innovation with the following specific objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to achieve a resource – and water - efficient and climate change resilient economy and society,

³¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/food-security-sustainable-agriculture-and-forestry-marine-maritime-and-inland-water>

³² <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/secure-clean-and-efficient-energy>

³³ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/smart-green-and-integrated-transport>

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the protection and sustainable management of natural resources and ecosystems, and • a sustainable supply and use of raw materials, in order to meet the needs of a growing global population within the sustainable limits of the planet's natural resources and eco-systems. <p>The 20th century's era of seemingly plentiful and cheap resources is coming to an end. The ability of the economy to adapt and become more climate change resilient, resource efficient and at the same time remain competitive depends on high levels of eco-innovation, of a societal, economic, organisational and technological nature. With the global market for eco-innovation worth around €1 trillion per annum and expected to triple by 2030, eco-innovation represents a major opportunity to boost competitiveness and job creation in European economies.</p> <p>To ensure EU added value and given the transnational and global nature of the climate and the environment, their scale and complexity, and the international dimension of the raw materials supply chain, activities have to be carried out at the Union level and beyond. Reducing resource use and environmental impacts, whilst increasing competitiveness, will require a decisive societal and technological transition to an economy based on a sustainable relationship between nature and human well-being.</p> <p>Innovation in these fields will provide opportunities for growth and jobs, as well as innovative options involving science, technology including of ICT, the economy, society, policy and governance.</p> <p>Research and innovation will cover the following broad lines of activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate Action - Informed decisions for a climate-resilient low-carbon society • Cultural Heritage - Engaging a new cultural heritage agenda for economic growth • Earth Observations - Crucial info on climate, energy, natural hazards and other societal challenge • Nature-Based Solutions - Providing viable solutions of natural ecosystems <p>Systemic Eco-Innovation - Generating and sharing economic and environmental benefits³⁴</p>
Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies	<i>Superclass</i> : "Horizon 2020 Societal challenges"	<p>It is the organisational setting for public project funding for research that responds to the challenge to "reduce inequality and social exclusion. 80 million people are at risk of poverty and 14 million young people are not in education, employment or training. We have not yet overcome the economic crisis which has led to unemployment rates of 12% in general and 20% among the youth.</p> <p>Reducing inequalities and social exclusion in Europe are crucial challenges for the future of Europe. At the same time, there is great potential for Europe through opportunities provided, for example, by new forms of innovation and by the engagement of citizens. Supporting inclusive, innovative and reflective societies is a prerequisite for a sustainable European integration.</p> <p>EU research and innovation will address social exclusion, discriminations and various forms of inequalities. It will explore new forms of innovation and strengthen the evidence base for the Innovation Union, the</p>

³⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/climate-action-environment-resource-efficiency-and-raw-materials>

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		<p>European Research Area and other relevant EU policies. It will promote coherent and effective cooperation with third countries. Finally, it will address the issues of memories, identities, tolerance and cultural heritage.</p> <p>In short, this Societal Challenge of the Horizon 2020 programme aims at fostering a greater understanding of Europe, by providing solutions and support inclusive, innovative and reflective European societies with an innovative public sector in a context of unprecedented transformations and growing global interdependencies.”³⁵</p>
<p>Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens.</p>	<p><i>Superclass</i> : “Horizon 2020 Societal challenges”</p>	<p>It is the organisational setting for public project funding for research that responds to the challenge to “undertake the research and innovation activities needed to protect our citizens, society and economy as well as our infrastructures and services, our prosperity, political stability and wellbeing.</p> <p>The primary aims of the Secure Societies Challenge are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to enhance the resilience of our society against natural and man-made disasters, ranging from the development of new crisis management tools to communication interoperability, and to develop novel solutions for the protection of critical infrastructure; • to fight crime and terrorism ranging from new forensic tools to protection against explosives; • to improve border security, ranging from improved maritime border protection to supply chain security and to support the Union's external security policies including through conflict prevention and peace building; • and to provide enhanced cyber-security, ranging from secure information sharing to new assurance models. <p>Securing the society against disasters is one of the central elements of the functioning of any society. There is barely any societal sector which is not to some extent concerned by disasters and related resilience and security issues.</p> <p>Fighting crime and terrorism requires new technologies and capabilities for fighting and preventing crime (including cyber-crime), illegal trafficking and terrorism (including cyber-terrorism), including understanding and tackling terrorist ideas and beliefs to also avoid aviation-related threats.</p> <p>The protection of the European borders requires the development of systems, equipment, tools, processes, and methods for rapid identification. This includes supply chain security in the context of the EU's customs policy.</p> <p>Furthermore, solutions will be developed to support the Union's external security policies in civilian tasks, ranging from civil protection to humanitarian relief, border management or peace-keeping and post-crisis stabilisation, including conflict prevention, peace-building and mediation.</p> <p>On Digital Security, this Challenge focuses on increasing the security of current applications, services and</p>

³⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/europe-changing-world-inclusive-innovative-and-reflective-societies>

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		<p>infrastructures by integrating state-of-the-art security solutions or processes, supporting the creation of lead markets & market incentives in Europe, following an end-user driven approach, including for instance law enforcement agencies, first responders, operators of critical infrastructures, ICT service providers, ICT manufacturers, market operators and citizens.</p> <p>This Challenge should bring together all security stakeholders: industry - including SMEs, research organisations, universities, as well as public authorities, non-governmental organisations and public and private organisations in the security domain. The active involvement of end-users is of high importance. The Secure Societies Challenge will contribute to the implementation of the policy goals of the Europe 2020 strategy, the Security Industrial Policy, the Internal Security Strategy and the Cyber Security Strategy.”³⁶</p>
Science with and for Society	<p><i>Superclass:</i> “Horizon 2020” <i>Overlaps:</i> “Horizon 2020 Societal Challenges”</p>	<p>It is the organisational setting for public project funding for research that responds to the objective to build effective cooperation between science and society, to recruit new talent for science and to pair scientific excellence with social awareness and responsibility.</p> <p>The ‘Science with and for Society’ programme will be instrumental in addressing the European societal challenges tackled by Horizon 2020, building capacities and developing innovative ways of connecting science to society. It will make science more attractive (notably to young people), increase society’s appetite for innovation, and open up further research and innovation activities.</p> <p>It allows all societal actors (researchers, citizens, policy makers, business, third sector organisations etc.) to work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes with the values, needs and expectations of European society. This approach to research and innovation is called Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI).³⁷</p>
Key Enabling Technologies	<p><i>Superclass:</i> “Horizon 2020” <i>Overlaps:</i> “Horizon 2020 Societal Challenges”</p>	<p>It is the organisational setting for public project funding for research that responds to the objective of implementing the six Key Enabling Technologies (KETs): micro and nanoelectronics, nanotechnology, industrial biotechnology, advanced materials, photonics, and advanced manufacturing technologies. They have applications in multiple industries and help tackle societal challenges. Countries and regions that fully exploit KETs will be at the forefront of creating advanced and sustainable economies. KETs provide the basis for innovation in a range of products across all industrial sectors. They underpin the shift to a greener economy, are instrumental in modernising Europe’s industrial base, and drive the development of entirely new industries. Their importance makes them a key element of European industrial policy.³⁸</p>
Seventh Framework Programme	<p><i>Superclass:</i> “Research Funding Program”</p>	<p>The Seventh Framework Programme for Research and Technological Development (FP7) is the EU’s main instrument for funding research in Europe and it will run from 2007-2013. FP7 is also designed to respond to Europe’s employment needs, competitiveness and quality of life.³⁹</p>

³⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/secure-societies-%E2%80%93-protecting-freedom-and-security-europe-and-its-citizens>

³⁷ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/science-and-society>

³⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/growth/industry/key-enabling-technologies_en

³⁹ http://ec.europa.eu/research/fp7/index_en.cfm?pg=understanding

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Sixth Framework Programme	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research Program"	The Sixth European Community Framework Programme (FP6) for Research, Technological Development and Demonstration is a collection of the actions at EU level to fund and promote research. FP6 is the frame for the EU activities in the field of science, research and innovation. With a budget of 17.5 billion Euros for the years 2002 - 2006 it represents about 4 to 5 percent of the overall expenditure on RTD in EU Member States. The main objective of FP6 is to contribute to the creation of the European Research Area (ERA) by improving integration and co-ordination of research in Europe which is so far largely fragmented. ⁴⁰
Research Project	<i>IsFundedBy:</i> "Research Funding Program"	A research project is a scientific investigation, usually using scientific methods, to achieve defined objectives. (http://dbpedia.org/ontology/ResearchProject)
Research topic	<i>IsFundedBy:</i> "Research Funding Programs" <i>TheSameAs:</i> "Research theme"	A research topic can be defined as a phenomenon or theme to be studied and it is usually broader and more general than a specific research problem ⁴¹
Research theme	<i>IsFundedBy:</i> "Research Funding Programs" <i>TheSameAs:</i> "Research topic" <i>Superclass:</i> "Horizon 2020" <i>Superclass:</i> "Themes"	A research theme can be defined as a phenomenon or topic to be studied and it is usually broader and more general than a specific research problem ³⁸
Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Science with and for Society"	Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) means that societal actors work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to better align both the process and its outcomes, with the values, needs and expectations of European society. RRI is an ambitious challenge for the creation of a Research and Innovation policy driven by the needs of society and engaging all societal actors via inclusive participatory approaches.
Institutional change	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Science with and for Society"	In Horizon 2020, institutional change concerns sustainable changes undertaken and implemented in organisations funding and performing research and innovation; examples include the introduction of specific rules, governance arrangements or practices favouring open access, gender equality, ethics, science education, or public engagement.
Health	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Health, demographic change and wellbeing" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Environment"	The EU is required by its founding treaty to ensure that human health is protected as part of all its policies, and to work with the EU countries to improve public health, prevent human illness and eliminate sources of danger to physical and mental health. The EU health strategy "Together for Health" supports the overall Europe 2020 strategy. Europe 2020 aims

⁴⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/research/fp6/pdf/fp6-in-brief_en.pdf

⁴¹ P. Ghauri, and K. Grønhaug, 2010. Research Methods in Business Studies: A Practical Guide. Financial Times Press/Prentice Hall.

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		to turn the EU into a smart, sustainable and inclusive economy promoting growth for all – one prerequisite of which is a population in good health. ⁴²
Demographic change	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Health, demographic change and wellbeing"	The European Union is facing unprecedented demographic changes (an ageing population, low birth rates, changing family structures and migration). In the light of these challenges it is important, both at EU and national level, to review and adapt existing policies. ⁴³ There are countless programmes for handling demographic change on the level of the European Union.
Wellbeing	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Health, demographic change and wellbeing" <i>IsPartOf:</i> "Health"	The wellbeing research topic aims to improve the lifelong health and wellbeing of all. High-quality and economically sustainable health and care systems, and opportunities for new jobs and growth are the aims of support to research and innovation in response to this challenge. They will make a major contribution to Europe 2020.
Food security	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy" <i>TheSameAs:</i> "Food safety" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Sustainable agriculture and forestry" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Marine and maritime research"	Food and nutrition security is about ensuring that everybody is able to access sufficient, affordable and nutritious food. Through its support, the EU seeks to build resilience to food crises and help countries ensure that no one is left hungry. In particular, fighting under-nutrition is vital to give the world's poorest children a chance to lead healthier lives, learn better and improve their future income opportunities. ⁴⁴
Sustainable agriculture and forestry	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Energy efficiency" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Low carbon technologies"	Sustainable agriculture aims to reduce poverty and hunger and promote inclusive growth, substantial investment in rural areas and in agriculture. Most poor and undernourished people live in rural areas, where small-scale farming forms the backbone of the economy. Well-planned and well-targeted investment in small-scale farming can, therefore, help a country feed itself and reduce its dependency on outside assistance. ⁴⁵ The research topic on forestry covers a range of research areas, including forest monitoring, harmonisation of forest information and assessment of the sustainable governance of European forests and their ecosystem services. ⁴⁶
Marine and maritime research	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Energy efficiency" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Low carbon technologies"	Marine and maritime research topic aims to attain the necessary scientific knowledge of the elements that define the state of the marine environment. Science must provide the knowledge upon which integrated management can build the tools for assessing progress towards Good Environmental Status. This knowledge will be developed, in particular, through the EU Strategy for Marine and Maritime Research (COM (2008) 534) in the framework of the Integrated Maritime Policy. ⁴⁷

⁴² http://ec.europa.eu/health/programme/policy_en

⁴³ <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=502&langId=en>

⁴⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/sectors/food-and-agriculture/food-and-nutrition-security_en

⁴⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/sectors/food-and-agriculture/sustainable-agriculture-and-rural-development_en

⁴⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/forestry>

⁴⁷ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/marine/research/index_en.htm

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Inland water research	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy"</p>	Inland water research topic addresses societal and economic challenges deriving from the evolving vulnerability of the European and global water environment. Water represents a societal challenge. On a planet where 70% of the surface is covered by water, only 1% of this amount is actually usable freshwater. In the European Union, water scarcity and droughts already affect one third of the European territory and yet, of the total abstraction of freshwater, 44% is used to cool thermal power plants and 24% for irrigation. As water scarcity and droughts regularly affect large parts of the European territory, water availability and its efficient use are also issues that need to be addressed in Europe. ⁴⁸
Bioeconomy	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the Bioeconomy" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Energy efficiency" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Low carbon technologies"</p>	Bioeconomy is Europe's response to key environmental challenges the world is facing already today. It is meant to reduce the dependence on natural resources, transform manufacturing, promote sustainable production of renewable resources from land, fisheries and aquaculture and their conversion into food, feed, fibre, bio-based products and bio-energy, while growing new jobs and industries. ⁴⁹
Energy efficiency	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Secure, clean and efficient energy" <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Smart cities" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Sustainable agriculture and forestry" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Marine and maritime research" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Bioeconomy" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Bioeconomy" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Smart cities"</p>	Energy efficiency research topic focuses on technology deployment and market uptake, and encompasses a broad range of activities which includes the European Energy Efficiency Platform, the Covenant of Mayors, the Building Design Competition, and the EU Codes of Conduct for ICT. ⁵⁰
Low carbon technologies	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Secure, clean and efficient energy" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Sustainable agriculture and forestry" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Marine and maritime research" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Bioeconomy" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Smart cities"</p>	New and innovative low carbon technologies help to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and create new employment and growth. Europe is a leading player in the area of low carbon technologies and we are maintaining our leading position with a range of policy initiatives. ⁵¹
Smart cities	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme"</p>	A smart city is a place where the traditional networks and services are made more efficient with the use of

⁴⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/water>

⁴⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/bioeconomy>

⁵⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/energy-efficiency>

⁵¹ https://ec.europa.eu/clima/policies/lowcarbon_en

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	<p><i>IsImplementedBy</i>: "Secure, clean and efficient energy" <i>Overlaps</i>: "Energy efficiency" <i>Overlaps</i>: "Low carbon technologies" <i>IsFosteredBy</i>: "Green Vehicles"</p>	<p>digital and telecommunication technologies, for the benefit of its inhabitants and businesses. With this vision in mind, the European Union is investing in ICT research and innovation and developing policies to improve the quality of life of citizens and make cities more sustainable in view of Europe's 20-20-20 targets. The smart city concept goes beyond the use of ICT for better resource use and less emissions. It means smarter urban transport networks, upgraded water supply and waste disposal facilities, and more efficient ways to light and heat buildings. And it also encompasses a more interactive and responsive city administration, safer public spaces and meeting the needs of an ageing population.⁵²</p>
Mobility	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy</i>: "Smart, green and integrated transport"</p>	<p>The European Commission is working towards forms of mobility that are sustainable, energy-efficient and respectful for the environment. Technical innovation such as electric vehicles, intelligent transport systems and smart grids, will contribute to achieving this goal. Alternative fuels like biofuels and non-polluting energy sources, notably hydrogen, are also pathways towards a more sustainable mobility.⁵³</p>
Green Vehicles	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy</i>: "Smart, green and integrated transport" <i>IsFosteredBy</i>: "Energy efficiency" <i>IsFosteredBy</i>: "Low carbon technologies"</p>	<p>The Green Vehicles research topic focuses on road transport research and innovation. It addresses the following road transport challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • improvements in energy efficiency • the use of new types on non-conventional energies (such as electricity, CNG, LNG, renewable and tailored fuels) • Research and innovation under this call will include: • advanced power-train technologies • new vehicle architecture <p>interfaces between the vehicle and the recharging infrastructure⁵⁴</p>
Fast Track Innovation in Transport	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy</i>: "Smart, green and integrated transport" <i>IsFosteredBy</i>: "Green Vehicles" <i>IsFosteredBy</i>: "Mobility"</p>	<p>The Fast Track to Innovation in Transport is a fully-bottom-up measure in Horizon 2020 to promote close-to-the-market innovation activities, and open to all types of participants.</p>
Climate action	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy</i>: "environment, resource efficiency and raw materials " <i>IsPartOf</i>: "Environment" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Ecotax"</p>	<p>The Climate action JRC is committed to supporting the EU in limiting global climate change. For example, it provides expertise in modelling and evaluation of different energy scenarios, black carbon assessment, land use change and carbon capture and storage.⁵⁵</p>

⁵² <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/smart-cities>

⁵³ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/sustainable-transport-and-fuels>

⁵⁴ <http://ec.europa.eu/inea/horizon-2020/green-vehicles>

⁵⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/climate-change-mitigation>

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Environment	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy :</i> "Climate action, resource efficiency and raw materials" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Ecotax"	Protection of the environment for future generations and efforts to limit the impacts of climate change are of the utmost importance in European and world policy. The Directorate General of the European Commission on Environment ('DG Environment') proposes policies and legislation that protect natural habitats, keep air and water clean, ensure proper waste disposal, improve knowledge about toxic chemicals, and help businesses move towards a sustainable economy. ⁵⁶
Resource efficiency	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy :</i> " Climate action, environment and raw materials " <i>IsPartOf:</i> "Environment"	Resource efficiency means using the Earth's limited resources in a sustainable manner while minimising impacts on the environment. It allows us to create more with less and to deliver greater value with less input. The resource-efficient Europe flagship initiative is part of the Europe 2020 Strategy, the EU's growth strategy for a smart, inclusive and sustainable economy. It supports the shift towards sustainable growth via a resource-efficient, low-carbon economy. ⁵⁷
Raw materials	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy :</i> " Climate action, environment and resource efficiency" <i>IsPartOf:</i> "Environment" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Ecotax"	Raw materials are essential to our everyday lives. Millions of European jobs rely on the availability of raw materials. They feed the industrial sector and all the economic activities downstream. Ensuring the security and the sustainability of the supply of raw materials is essential. The EU's raw materials policies aim to help raise industry's contribution to EU GDP to around 20% by 2020. ⁵⁸
Inclusive societies	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy :</i> " Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies "	The research topic on Inclusive societies addresses the following issues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster a smart, sustainable and inclusive growth • Build inclusive and flexible societies in Europe • Strengthen the role played by Europe on the world stage • Bridging the gaps in research and innovation in Europe. (http://www.apre.it/5497)
Innovative societies	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy :</i> "Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies "	The research topic on Innovative societies addresses the following issues: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen the knowledge and measures in support of the Innovation Union and the European Research Area • Exploring new forms of innovation that includes social innovation and creativity • Ensure the participation of society in research and innovation • Promote a consistent and effective cooperation with third countries. (http://www.apre.it/5497)
Reflective societies	<i>Superclass:</i> "Research theme"	The research topic on Reflective societies addresses the following issues:

⁵⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/basics/home_en.htm

⁵⁷ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/resource_efficiency/index_en.htm

⁵⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/raw-materials>

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	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies "	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze the legacy, memory, identity, integration and interaction of European culture, including its representations in scientific and cultural collections, archives and museums, to better inform and better understand the present through interpretations of the past Carry out research on the history, literature, art, philosophy and religion of European countries and regions, and how these have originated the diversity of today Conducting research on the European role in the world, the mutual influences and links between global regions and provide an external glance on European cultures.. (http://www.apre.it/5497)
Infrastructure protection	<i>Superclass</i> : "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Security" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Digital Security"	Critical infrastructures include power grids, the transport network and information and communication systems. Protection of these infrastructures is vital for the security of the EU and the well-being of its citizens. ⁵⁹
Security	<i>Superclass</i> : "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens"	Europe has never been so peacefully consolidated, and the levels of security enjoyed by European citizens are high, compared to other parts of the world. However, Europe's vulnerability continues to exist in a context of ever-increasing globalisation in which societies are facing security threats and challenges that are growing in scale and sophistication. The specific objective of this area is to foster secure European societies in a context of unprecedented transformations and growing global interdependencies and threats, while strengthening the European culture of freedom and justice. ⁶⁰
Digital security	<i>Superclass</i> : "Research theme" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens" <i>IsPartOf</i> : "Security"	Cybersecurity research provides support to the EU to respond to cyber-attacks and reinforce rules on personal data protection, as well as to ensure that critical networked systems are sufficiently secure and resilient. ⁶¹

RRI Dimensions: Responsible Research and Innovation keys as defined in

https://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_public_engagement/responsible-research-and-innovation-leaflet_en.pdf and related concepts

RRI Dimension	<i>SpecifiedIn</i> : " Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)"	Key concept for RRI. The definition is based on Klaasen et al (2014): Policy brief on the state of the art on
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⁵⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/critical-infrastructure-protection>

⁶⁰ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/area/security>

⁶¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/research-topic/cybersecurity>

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		RRI and a working definition of RRI. D.2.2. RRI-Tools.EU. Athena Institute, Vu University Amsterdam. Box 2B, p. 6.
Public engagement	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "RRI Dimension"</p> <p><i>Superclass:</i> (from World Bank Thesaurus): "Participation and Empowerment"</p> <p><i>Superclass:</i> (from World Bank Thesaurus): "Social Inclusion and Social Policy"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Public Accountability"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Responsibility"</p>	"The process of R&I is collaborative and multi-actor: all societal actors (researchers, citizens, policymakers, industry, educators, etc.) work together during the whole research and innovation process in order to align its outcomes to the values, needs and expectations of European society"
Citizen Science	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Public engagement"</p> <p><i>TheSameAs:</i> "Participatory Research" (from UNESCO Thesaurus)</p> <p><i>Superclass:</i> "Research"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Community participation"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Science education"</p>	<p>Citizen science is scientific research conducted, in whole or in part, by amateur (or nonprofessional) scientists. Citizen science is sometimes described as "public participation in scientific research," participatory monitoring and participatory action research. The concept is based in two dimensions of the relationship between citizens and science: 1) that science should be responsive to citizens' concerns and needs; and 2) that citizens themselves could produce reliable scientific knowledge. A citizen scientist is therefore a member of the general public who engages in scientific work, often in collaboration with or under the direction of professional scientists and scientific institutions; an amateur scientist. Many citizen science projects serve education and outreach goals. These projects may be designed for a formal classroom environment or an informal education environment such as museums.</p> <p>The concept of citizen science is strongly linked with RRI has it also comprehends the participation of non-scientists in the process of gathering data according to specific scientific protocols and in the process of using and interpreting that data, the engagement of non-scientists in true decision-making about policy issues that have technical or scientific components, and the engagement of research scientists in the democratic and policy process.</p> <p>Citizen science also relates to a fundamental point of RRI: Ethics. Citizen science projects have a genuine science outcome. For example, answering a research question or informing conservation action, management decisions or environmental policy. Both the professional scientists and the citizen scientists benefit from taking part. Benefits may include the publication of research outputs, learning opportunities, personal enjoyment, social benefits, satisfaction through contributing to scientific evidence e.g. to address local, national and international issues, and through that, the potential to influence policy. Citizen scientists receive feedback from the project. For example, how their data are being used and what the research, policy or societal outcomes are. . (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Citizen_science)</p>
Citizen Observatory	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Public engagement"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Participatory Research"</p> <p><i>Superclass:</i> "Research"</p>	Citizen observatories are sets of ICT-tools to collect, analyse and visualise sensor data, with the aim of improving the quality of life of citizens. Participatory sensing is the driving technology behind citizen observatories. It allows people-centric contextual monitoring by way of smart mobile devices.

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	<i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Community participation" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Science education"	(http://citizen-observatory.be/index.php/citizen-observatories/)
Gender equality	<i>Superclass</i> : "RRI Dimension" <i>Superclass</i> : "Equal opportunity". (from IEEE Thesaurus) <i>Superclass</i> : "Equality". (from World Bank Thesaurus) <i>TheSameAs</i> : "Gender equal opportunity" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Equality policy" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Gender neutrality" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Gender equity" (from World Bank Thesaurus) <i>Concerns</i> : "Gender" (from Gender Equality glossary and thesaurus)	"The ideal of gender equality in RRI is a society where the representation of masculine and feminine values in research and innovation are balanced. Issues addressed by this policy agenda challenge people to think about the gendered nature of behaviours, discourse, products, technologies, environments, and knowledge." (RRI Tools project: https://www.rri-tools.eu/documents/21503/103925/RRI_Tools_Policy_Brief_EN.pdf/708f2fe7-6440-41b0-b583-697f72748e03)
Gender balance	<i>Superclass</i> : "Gender equality"	Gender balance is commonly used in reference to human resources and equal participation of women and men in all areas of work, projects or programmes.
Science education	<i>Superclass</i> : "RRI Dimension" <i>Superclass</i> : "Education" (from World Bank Thesaurus and ERIC Thesaurus) <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Open Science" <i>Overlaps</i> : "Education for sustainable development"	"Science Education: Focuses on (1) enhancing the current education process to better equip citizens with the necessary knowledge and skills so they can participate in R&I debates; and (2) increasing the number of researchers (promote scientific vocations)." (RRI Tools project: https://www.rri-tools.eu/documents/21503/103925/RRI_Tools_Policy_Brief_EN.pdf/708f2fe7-6440-41b0-b583-697f72748e03)
Environmental education	<i>Superclass</i> : "Science education" (from UNESCO Thesaurus)	It refers to organized efforts to teach how natural environments function, and particularly, how human beings can manage behavior and ecosystems to live sustainably.
Marine education	<i>Superclass</i> : "Science education" (from UNESCO Thesaurus and ERIC Thesaurus)	It is the process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits on marine environment.
Technical education	<i>Superclass</i> : "Science education" (from ERIC Thesaurus)	The training of engineers and technicians for work in industry, construction, transportation, communications, agriculture, and forestry.
Open access	<i>Superclass</i> : "RRI Dimension" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Open Science" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Ethics of science" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Public policy"	"Open Access addresses issues of accessibility to and ownership of scientific information. Free and earlier access to scientific work might improve the quality of scientific research and facilitate fast innovation, constructive collaborations among peers, and productive dialogue with civil society." (RRI Tools project: https://www.rri-tools.eu/documents/21503/103925/RRI_Tools_Policy_Brief_EN.pdf/708f2fe7-6440-41b0-b583-697f72748e03)
Ethics	<i>Superclass</i> : "RRI Dimension" <i>Superclass</i> : "Philosophy" (from Power Thesaurus and ERIC Thesaurus) <i>TheSameAs</i> : "Moral philosophy"	"Ethics: focuses on (1) research integrity: the prevention of unacceptable research and research practices; and (2) science and society: the ethical acceptability of scientific and technological developments. ⁶² (RRI Tools project: https://www.rri-tools.eu/documents/21503/103925/RRI_Tools_Policy_Brief_EN.pdf/)

⁶² <http://www.rri-tools.eu/about-rri>

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	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Moral values" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Morality" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Deontology" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Moral development"	708f2fe7-6440-41b0-b583-697f72748e03)
Ethics of science	<i>Superclass</i> : "Ethics"	<i>Ethics of Science</i> is the study of ethics in science and scientific research. ⁶³
Governance	<i>Superclass</i> : "RRI Dimension" <i>Superclass</i> : "Social control". (from Power Thesaurus) <i>TheSameAs</i> : "Public policy" <i>TheSameAs</i> : "Government policy" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Ethics" (from UNESCO Thesaurus) <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Civil society" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Participatory development" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Political power" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Public participation" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Public accountability"	"Governance: To reach futures that are both acceptable and desirable, governance arrangements have to (1) be robust and adaptable to the unpredictable development of R&I (de facto governance); (2) be familiar enough to align with existing practices in R&I; (3) share responsibility and accountability among all actors; and (4) provide governance instruments to actually foster this shared responsibility." (RRI Tools project: https://www.rri-tools.eu/documents/21503/103925/RRI_Tools_Policy_Brief_EN.pdf/708f2fe7-6440-41b0-b583-697f72748e03)
Corporate Governance	<i>Superclass</i> : "Governance"	Corporate governance broadly refers to the mechanisms, processes and relations by which corporations are controlled and directed. Governance structures and principles identify the distribution of rights and responsibilities among different participants in the corporation (such as the board of directors, managers, shareholders, creditors, auditors, regulators, and other stakeholders) and includes the rules and procedures for making decisions in corporate affairs.
Public policy	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Governance" (from UNESCO Thesaurus) <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Political power" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Institutional change" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Public participation" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Public accountability"	Public policy is the principled guide to action taken by the administrative executive branches of the state with regard to a class of issues, in a manner consistent with law and institutional customs. The foundation of public policy is composed of national constitutional laws and regulations. Further substrates include both judicial interpretations and regulations which are generally authorized by legislation. Public policy is considered strong when it solves problems efficiently and effectively, serves justice, supports governmental institutions and policies, and encourages active citizenship. [1] Other scholars define public policy as a system of "courses of action, regulatory measures, laws, and funding priorities concerning a given topic promulgated by a governmental entity or its representatives." [2] Public policy is commonly embodied in "constitutions, legislative acts, and judicial decisions." (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_policy)
Equality policy	<i>Superclass</i> : "Public policy"	A framework for realising gender equality and equity into its policies, structures, systems

⁶³ D. B. Resnik, *The ethics of science: An introduction*. Routledge. (2005)

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		and operations. ⁶⁴
Social Policy	<i>Superclass:</i> "Public policy"	Social policy is a term which is applied to various areas of policy, usually within a governmental or political setting (such as the welfare state and study of social services). [1] It can refer to guidelines, principles, legislation and activities that affect the living conditions conducive to human welfare, such as a person's quality of life. The Department of Social Policy at the London School of Economics defines social policy as "an interdisciplinary and applied subject concerned with the analysis of societies' responses to social need", which seeks to foster in its students a capacity to understand theory and evidence drawn from a wide range of social science disciplines, including economics, sociology, psychology, geography, history, law, philosophy and political science.[2] The Malcolm Wiener Center for Social Policy at Harvard University describes social policy as "public policy and practice in the areas of health care, human services, criminal justice, inequality, education, and labour".[3] Social policy might also be described as actions that affect the well-being of members of a society through shaping the distribution of and access to goods and resources in that society.[4] Social policy often deals with wicked problems.[5] (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_policy)
Social Inclusion	<i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Social Policy" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Equality Policy"	Social Inclusion and Social Policy works toward a critical and theoretical understanding of cultural, political, and social processes which can be used to assess and improve the effectiveness of social policies. This profile should include terms that reflect the methodology of social analysis and its effects on and translation into policy, such as the results and impact of a study on a particular social issue. This sub-topic also includes state policies on family size, abortion, euthanasia and the death penalty, and policies concerning equal rights and inclusion for the economically and socially disadvantaged, including ethnic, religious and sexual minorities.
Sustainability	<i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Social Policy"	"to what extent (...) a research field, a research programme or an RRI initiative contribute to inclusive and sustainable growth" (Strand et al 2015, http://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_rri/rri_indicators_final_version.pdf , p. 37).
Environmental sustainability	<i>Superclass:</i> "Sustainability" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Integral cycle of water" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Maritime-zoning" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "The good city" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Science Education" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Ecotax"	Environmental sustainability is the maintenance of the factors and practices that contribute to the quality of environment on a long-term basis. (http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/environmental-sustainability.html)
Social justice	<i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Institutional change" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Social Policy" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Equality Policy"	"Social justice directly in the context of research activities can be considered from two perspectives: (a) the relationship between the researchers and the research subjects; and (b) the participation of social groups in benefits arising from research. The first perspective is concerned with researchers unfairly taking advantage

⁶⁴ http://thecommonwealth.org/sites/default/files/page/documents/Commonwealth_Secretariat_Gender_Equality_Policy.pdf

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		<p>of research subjects and imposing unfair burdens on them for their own (...):</p> <p>Is the new technology/product accessible/affordable to wide variety of different social groups?</p> <p>Is the research problem addressing an access problem of a disadvantaged social group, such as disabled people, illiterate people, migrants, elderly people, etc.?</p> <p>Does the research have the potential to impact negatively on some social groups?</p> <p>Measuring the impact should focus on two issues: (a) whether researchers consider at all the impact of their research on social justice; and (b) whether they have taken any steps to either extend the impact of their research to a larger population or to minimise potential unintended negative consequences in relation to social justice."</p> <p>(Strand et al 2015, http://ec.europa.eu/research/swafs/pdf/pub_rri/rri_indicators_final_version.pdf, p. 39)</p>
Administration	<i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Institutional change"	The management of public affairs; government.
Public administration	<i>Superclass</i> : "Administration" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Governance" (from UNESCO Thesaurus)	Public administration is the implementation of government policy and also an academic discipline that studies this implementation and prepares civil servants for working in the public service. As a "field of inquiry with a diverse scope" its "fundamental goal... is to advance management and policies so that government can function." Some of the various definitions which have been offered for the term are: "the management of public programs"; the "translation of politics into the reality that citizens see every day"; and "the study of government decision making, the analysis of the policies themselves, the various inputs that have produced them, and the inputs necessary to produce alternative policies."
Political system	<i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Institutional change" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Political power"	A political system is a system of politics and government. It is usually compared to the legal system, economic system, cultural system, and other social systems. However, this is a very simplified view of a much more complex system of categories involving the questions of who should have authority and what the government's influence on its people and economy should be.
Parliamentary government	<i>Superclass</i> : "Parliamentary government"	Parliamentary government is a system of government having the real executive power vested in a cabinet composed of members of the legislature who are individually and collectively responsible to the legislature.
Political power	<i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Institutional change"	An authority held by a group within a society that allows for the administration of public resources and implement policies for society. Power may be acquired as a means of governmental direction or in opposition to a government group. (http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/political-power.html)
Social control	<i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Institutional change" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Political power"	Roodenburg identifies the concept of social control as a classical concept. ⁶⁵ While the concept of social control has been around since the formation of organized sociology, the meaning has been altered over time. Originally, the concept simply referred to society's ability to regulate itself. ⁶⁶ However, in the 1930s, the term took on its more modern meaning of an individual's conversion to conformity. Social control theory began to be studied as a separate field in the early 20th century.

⁶⁵ H. Roodenburg. text. published by Ohio State University Press 2004, ISBN 0814209688. Retrieved 2015-11-29.

⁶⁶ Morris Janowitz (Jul 1975). "Sociological Theory and Social Control". *American Journal of Sociology. The University of Chicago Press Article. 81 (1): 82–108.* doi:10.1086/226035

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Monitoring	<i>IsActuatedBy</i> : "Political power"	Develop a performing monitoring system of water quality capable to assimilate in situ and satellite data from stations (making use of the opportunities of Sentinel missions)
Accountability		The obligation of an individual or organization to account for its activities, accept responsibility for them, and to disclose the results in a transparent manner. It also includes the responsibility for money or other entrusted property. (http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/accountability.html)
Public Accountability	<i>Superclass</i> : "Accountability" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Science Education"	The obligations of agencies and public enterprises who have been trusted with the public resources, to be answerable to the fiscal and the social responsibilities that have been assigned to them. These companies and agencies need to be accountable to the public at large and carry out the duties asked of them responsibly. http://thelawdictionary.org/public-accountability/
Research	<i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Science education" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Research Funding Program" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Research Project" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Open Access" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Open Science"	The systematic investigation into and study of materials and sources in order to establish facts and reach new conclusions. (https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/research)
Participatory Research	<i>Superclass</i> : "Research"	Social research in which the persons being studied are also fully involved in the research design and analysis.
Gender		Gender refers to the social attributes and opportunities associated with being female and male and to the relationships between women and men and girls and boys, as well as to the relations between women and those between men.
Gender equity	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Equality Policy"	Gender equity entails the provision of fairness and justice in the distribution of benefits and responsibilities between women and men. The concept recognises that women and men have different needs and power and that these differences should be identified and addressed in a manner that rectifies the imbalances between the sexes. This may include equal treatment, or treatment that is different but considered equivalent in terms of rights, benefits, obligations and opportunities.
Gender neutrality	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Equality Policy"	Gender neutrality (adjective form: gender-neutral), also known as gender-neutralism or the gender neutrality movement, describes the idea that policies, language, and other social institutions should avoid distinguishing roles according to people's sex or gender, in order to avoid discrimination arising from the impression that there are social roles for which one gender is more suited than another. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gender_neutrality)
Education		It is the process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits.
Education for sustainable development	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Science Education" <i>Overlaps</i> : "Science education"	"Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) is a learning process (or approach to teaching) based on the ideals and principles that underlie sustainability and is concerned with all levels and types of learning to provide quality education and foster sustainable human development – learning to know, learning to be, learning to live together, learning to do and learning to transform oneself and society."

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		<p>ESD is a vision of education that seeks to empower people to assume responsibility for creating a sustainable future. Central to ESD is the concept of culture as an essential underlying theme. It has been acknowledged that there is no “single route” to sustainable development. Further, it is coherent that understandings of and visions for sustainability will be different for each of us and that we will need to work together to negotiate the process of achieving sustainability.</p> <p>The concept of sustainable development has gained notable popularity since the United Nations World Commission on Environment and Development (Our Common Future) Report of 1987 and the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development of 1992 (otherwise known as the Rio Earth Summit), that gave rise to the most recognised and referred to definition of:</p> <p>“Sustainable development is development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.” (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987, http://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/jid.3380010208/full)</p>
Moral values	<p><i>IsImplementedBy:</i> “Social responsibility” <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> “Moral development” <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Morality” <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Conscience”</p>	<p>Moral values refer to a set of principles that guide an individual on how to evaluate right versus wrong. People generally apply moral values to justify decisions, intentions and actions, and it also defines the personal character of a person. An individual with high moral values typically displays characteristics of integrity, courage, respect, fairness, honesty and compassion.</p>
Morality	<p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Deontology”</p>	<p>Morality (from the Latin <i>moralis</i> “manner, character, proper behavior”) is the differentiation of intentions, decisions, and actions between those that are distinguished as proper and those that are improper.⁶⁷ Morality can be a body of standards or principles derived from a code of conduct from a particular philosophy, religion, or culture, or it can derive from a standard that a person believes should be universal.⁶⁸ Morality may also be specifically synonymous with “goodness” or “rightness”.</p>
Deontology	<p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Morality” <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Moral values” <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Ethics”</p>	<p>Deontological ethics or deontology (from Greek <i>δέον</i>, <i>deon</i>, “obligation, duty”) is the normative ethical position that judges the morality of an action based on rules.</p>
Theatre of the Oppressed		<p>The Theatre of the Oppressed is an artistic performance as a mean of promoting social and political change. In the Theatre of the Oppressed, the audience becomes active, such that as “spect-actors” they explore, show, analyse and transform the reality in which they are living (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Theatre_of_the_Oppressed).</p> <p>A Theatre of the Oppressed can be used as a method to engage the general public and other stakeholders in the decision-making process related to an issue to which they are associated to the causes or consequences. By taking an active part in the performance, the “spect-actors” will have the responsibilities</p>

⁶⁷<http://www.unesco.org/education/esd-unit/definition-of-esd/>

⁶⁷ Long, A. A.; Sedley, D. N. (1987). *The Hellenistic Philosophers: Translations of the Principal Sources with Philosophical Commentary*. 1. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. pp. 366–367. ISBN 9780521275569.

⁶⁸ Stanford University (14 March 2011). “*The Definition of Morality*”. *Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*. Stanford University. Retrieved 22 March 2014.

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		of understand the details of the issue and the different perceptions existing and will also have the benefit of stating a position, lobbying and influencing a decision.
Moral development	<i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Morality" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Moral values"	Moral development focuses on the emergence, change, and understanding of morality from infancy through adulthood. In the field of moral development, morality is defined as principles for how individuals ought to treat one another, with respect to justice, others' welfare, and rights. In order to investigate how individuals understand morality, it is essential to measure their beliefs, emotions, attitudes, and behaviors that contribute to moral understanding. The field of moral development studies the role of peers and parents in facilitating moral development, the role of conscience and values, socialization and cultural influences, empathy and altruism, and positive development. The interest in morality spans many disciplines (e.g., philosophy, economics, biology, and political science) and specializations within psychology (e.g., social, cognitive, and cultural). Moral developmental psychology research focuses on questions of origins and change in morality across the lifespan.
Conscience		Conscience is an aptitude, faculty, intuition or judgment that assists in distinguishing right from wrong. Moral judgment may derive from values or norms (principles and rules). In psychological terms conscience is often described as leading to feelings of remorse when a human commits actions that go against his/her moral values and to feelings of rectitude or integrity when actions conform to such norms. The extent to which conscience informs moral judgment before an action and whether such moral judgments are or should be based in reason has occasioned debate through much of the history of Western philosophy.
Formal learning	<i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Open Science" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Science Education"	Normally delivered by trained teachers in a systematic intentional way within a school, academy/college/institute or university, is one of three forms of learning the others being informal learning, which typically takes place naturally as part of some other activity, and non-formal learning, which includes everything else, such as sports instruction provided by non-trained educators without a formal curriculum. The process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits. Educational methods include storytelling, discussion, teaching, training, and directed research. Education frequently takes place under the guidance of educators, but learners may also educate themselves (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Education ; https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Formal_learning)
Civil society		Civil society is the "aggregate of non-governmental organizations and institutions that manifest interests and will of citizens." ⁶⁹ Civil society includes the family and the private sphere, referred to as the "third sector" of society, distinct from government and business. ⁷⁰ By other authors, "civil society" is used in the sense of 1) the aggregate of non-governmental organizations and institutions that manifest interests and will of citizens or 2) individuals and organizations in a society which are independent of the government.
Responsibility	<i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Science Education"	A duty or obligation to satisfactorily perform or complete a task (assigned by someone, or created by one's

⁶⁹ [Civil society – Define Civil society at Dictionary.com](#). Dictionary.com.

⁷⁰ [What is Civil Society](#) civilsoc.org Archived 2 May 2009 at the [Wayback Machine](#).

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	<i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Ethics"	own promise or circumstances) that one must fulfil, and which has a consequent penalty for failure. (http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/responsibility.html)
Social responsibility	<i>Superclass</i> : "Responsibility" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Civil society"	Social responsibility is an ethical framework and suggests that an entity, be it an organization or individual, has an obligation to act for the benefit of society at large. Social responsibility is a duty every individual has to perform so as to maintain a balance between the economy and the ecosystems. A trade-off may exist between economic development, in the material sense, and the welfare of the society and environment,[1] though this has been challenged by many reports over the past decade.[2][3] Social responsibility means sustaining the equilibrium between the two. It pertains not only to business organizations but also to everyone whose any action impacts the environment.[4] This responsibility can be passive, by avoiding engaging in socially harmful acts, or active, by performing activities that directly advance social goals. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Social_responsibility)
Public awareness	<i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Science education" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Open Access" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Public engagement"	Public awareness of science, public understanding of science, or more recently, Public Engagement with Science and Technology are terms relating to the attitudes, behaviours, opinions, and activities that comprise the relations between the general public or lay society as a whole to scientific knowledge and organisation. It is a comparatively new approach to the task of exploring the multitude of relations and linkages science, technology, and innovation have among the general public. While earlier work in the discipline had focused on augmenting public knowledge of scientific topics, in line with the information deficit model of science communication, the discrediting of the model has led to an increased emphasis on how the public chooses to use scientific knowledge and on the development of interfaces to mediate between expert and lay understandings of an issue. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_awareness_of_science)
Public participation	<i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Science awareness"	Public participation is a political principle or practice, and may also be recognised as a right (right to public participation). The terms public participation, often called P2 by practitioners, is sometimes used interchangeably with the concept or practice of stakeholder engagement and/or popular participation. Generally public participation seeks and facilitates the involvement of those potentially affected by or interested in a decision. This can be in relation to individuals, governments, institutions, companies or any other entities that affect public interests. The principle of public participation holds that those who are affected by a decision have a right to be involved in the decision-making process. Public participation implies that the public's contribution will influence the decision.[1][2] Public participation may be regarded as a way of empowerment and as vital part of democratic governance.[2] In the context of knowledge management the establishment of ongoing participatory processes is seen by some in the facilitator of collective intelligence and inclusiveness, shaped by the desire for the participation of the whole community or society.[2] Public participation is part of "people centred" or "human centric" principles, which have emerged in Western culture over the last thirty years, and has had some bearings of education, business, public policy

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		and international relief and development programs. Public participation is advanced by the humanist movements. Public participation may be advanced as part of a “people first” paradigm shift. In this respect public participation may challenge the concept that “big is better” and the logic of centralized hierarchies, advancing alternative concepts of “more heads are better than one” and arguing that public participation can sustain productive and durable change.[3] (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Public_participation)
Participation in cultural life	<i>Superclass:</i> “Public participation” <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Science education” <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> “Civil society”	A freedom to participate in cultural life and as a right to access the set of major artworks of a given community.
Community participation	<i>Superclass:</i> “Public participation” (from UNESCO Thesaurus) (from World Bank Thesaurus) <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> “Civil society”	The involvement of people in a community in projects to solve their own problems ⁷¹ .
Participatory development	<i>Superclass:</i> “Public participation” (from UNESCO Thesaurus) <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Civil society”	An all-encompassing label used to describe the various mechanisms that individuals or groups may use to communicate their views on a public issue. According to Pring and Noé (Pring and Noé, 2002)[1], public participation is an “all-encompassing label used to describe the various mechanisms that individuals or groups may use to communicate their views on a public issue”. In the book Human Rights in Natural Resources, Pring and Noé recognize the difficulty of defining public participation, which is why their definition is not very precise. Sherry Arnstein, well-known for her article “A Ladder of Citizen Participation” (1969)[2], defines citizen participation as “the redistribution of power that enables the have-not citizens, presently excluded from the political and economic processes, to be deliberately included in the future”. It needs to be noted that Arnstein’s definition is rather old and that the public is not completely “excluded” anymore from “political and economic process”. Also, the public may include other types of actors than mere citizens. The fact that she mentions citizen “power” in her definition makes it relevant still because that is what participation is about; giving the public more power in decision-making. She also emphasizes the promotion of public participation, which was in her time of greater importance because it was still a relatively new concept. Public participation means different things to different people.(http://www.coastalwiki.org/wiki/Public_participation)
Political participation	<i>Superclass:</i> “Public participation” (from World Bank Thesaurus) <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Community participation” <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Civil society”	Any individual or collective involvement in the political process. Research on political participation suggests a hierarchy of modes of participation. Thus while a majority of members of most societies participate in political discussions and in elections, relatively few are active in more formal political roles.
Public participation in decision making	<i>Superclass:</i> “Public participation” <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Community participation” <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> “Political participation”	An all-encompassing label used to describe the various mechanisms that individuals or groups may use to communicate their views on a public issue. According to Pring and Noé (Pring and Noé, 2002) ^[1] , public participation is an “all-encompassing label used to describe the various mechanisms that individuals or

⁷¹ http://ec.europa.eu/echo/files/evaluation/watsan2005/annex_files/WEDC/es/ES12CD.pdf

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	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Participation and Empowerment"	groups may use to communicate their views on a public issue". In the book Human Rights in Natural Resources, Pring and Noé recognize the difficulty of defining public participation, which is why their definition is not very precise. Sherry Arnstein, well-known for her article "A Ladder of Citizen Participation" (1969) ⁷² , defines citizen participation as "the redistribution of power that enables the have-not citizens, presently excluded from the political and economic processes, to be deliberately included in the future". It needs to be noted that Arnstein's definition is rather old and that the public is not completely "excluded" anymore from "political and economic process". Also, the public may include other types of actors than mere citizens. The fact that she mentions citizen "power" in her definition makes it relevant still because that is what participation is about; giving the public more power in decision-making. She also emphasizes the promotion of public participation, which was in her time of greater importance because it was still a relatively new concept. Public participation means different things to different people.(http://www.coastalwiki.org/wiki/Public_participation)
Participation and Empowerment	<i>Superclass</i> : "Public participation" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Civil society"	They are the essential building blocks for grassroots, people-oriented transformative development. ⁷²
Open Science	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Open Access" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> : "Science with and for Society"	Open science is the movement to make scientific research, data and dissemination accessible to all levels of an inquiring society, amateur or professional. It encompasses practices such as publishing open research, campaigning for open access, encouraging scientists to practice open notebook science, and generally making it easier to publish and communicate scientific knowledge. The European-funded project Facilitate Open Science Training for European Research (FOSTER) has developed an open science taxonomy as an attempt to map the open science field. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Open_science)
Public domain software	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Open Access"	It is software that has been placed in the public domain: in other words, there is absolutely no ownership such as copyright, trademark, or patent. Software in the public domain can be modified, distributed, or sold even without any attribution by anyone; this is unlike the common case of software under exclusive copyright, where software licenses grant limited usage rights.
Marine Related Issues: major empirical issues affecting maritime affairs in challenging ways derived from the EU Blue Growth Strategy, that is part of the Integrated Maritime Policy		
Marine Issues		Major empirical issues affecting maritime affairs in challenging ways derived from the EU Blue Growth Strategy, that is part of the Integrated Maritime Policy
Blue Growth	<i>Superclass</i> : "Marine Issues"	"Blue Growth is the long term strategy to support sustainable growth in the marine and maritime sectors as

⁷² Parpart, J., S. Rai and K. Staudt (2002) 'Rethinking Em(power)ment, Gender and Development. An Introduction', in Rethinking Empowerment: Gender and Development in a Global/Local World. London, UK: Routledge

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	<p><i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Marine Biotech" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Fishing and Aquaculture" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Sea Transportation" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Deep Sea Mining" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Bioprospecting" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Blue energy" <i>IsImplementedBy:</i> " Maritime, coastal and cruise tourism" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>a whole. Seas and oceans are drivers for the European economy and have great potential for innovation and growth. It is the maritime contribution to achieving the goals of the Europe 2020 strategy for smart, sustainable and inclusive growth."⁷³</p>
Biotechnology	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues"</p>	<p>'The application of science and technology to living organisms from marine resources, as well as parts, products and models thereof, to alter living or non-living materials for the production of knowledge, goods and services.'</p>
Marine Biotech	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>IsPartOf:</i> "Biotechnology"</p>	<p>"Marine biotechnology is a subset of biotechnology and, in line with the OECD definition of biotechnology, can be defined as: 'The application of science and technology to living organisms from marine resources, as well as parts, products and models thereof, to alter living or non-living materials for the production of knowledge, goods and services.'⁷⁴ This broad definition incorporating both modern and traditional activities ranging from conventional biological applications, like welfare and food production, as well as applications at the biomolecular and genomic level. The fast growing modern biotechnology provides new and improved utilisation where the enabling technology harnesses biomolecular processes for the development of knowledge and products such as food improvements, biofuels and biologics with better social and environmental benefits"⁷⁵</p>
Sea Transportation	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies" <i>Superclass:</i> "Transport"</p>	<p>"Any movement of goods and/or passengers using seagoing vessels on voyages which are undertaken wholly or partly at sea".⁷⁶</p>

⁷³ http://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/policy/blue_growth_en

⁷⁴ OECD definition: <http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=219>

⁷⁵ 'Marine biotechnology as a subset of biotechnology in general', 2014. Marine Biotechnology ERANET

(<http://www.marinebiotech.eu/sites/marinebiotech.eu/files/public/D3.7%20Definition%20of%20marine%20biotechnology%20as%20a%20subset%20of%20biotechnology%20in%20general.pdf>)

⁷⁶ <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=4277>

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Deep Sea Mining	<i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues"	Deep sea mining can be defined as: "mineral exploitation in the deep sea. The mining for mineral resources and the disposal of waste materials are the major potential sources of environmental hazard for the deep-sea system. Polymetallic nodules, manganese crusts, metalliferous sulphidic muds and massive consolidated sulphides might serve as exploitable sources of various metals, whilst phosphorite deposits represent a further resource" ⁷⁷
Bioprospecting	<i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>Concerns:</i> "Biodiversity"	"Bioprospecting can be defined as the systematic search for and development of new sources of chemical compounds, genes, micro-organisms, macro-organisms, and other valuable products from nature. It entails the search for economically valuable genetic and biochemical resources from nature. So, in brief, bioprospecting means looking for ways to commercialize biodiversity. Lately, exploration and research on indigenous knowledge related to the utilization and management of biological resources has also been included into the concept of bioprospecting. Thus, bioprospecting touches upon the conservation and sustainable use of biological resources and the rights of local and indigenous communities" ⁷⁸
Climate Change	<i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Oil and Gas" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Energy" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Transport" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Social responsibility" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Public awareness" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Conscience" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Moral values" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Education for sustainable development" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Research" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Administration" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Ethics" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Science education" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Ecotax"	A change in the state of the climate that can be identified (e.g., by using statistical tests) by changes in the mean and/or the variability of its properties and that persists for an extended period, typically decades or longer. Climate change may be due to natural internal processes or external forcings, or to persistent anthropogenic changes in the composition of the atmosphere or in land use. ⁷⁹ On Earth, human activities are changing the natural greenhouse effect. Over the last century the burning of fossil fuels like coal and oil has increased the concentration of atmospheric carbon dioxide. To a lesser extent, the clearing of land for agriculture, industry, and other human activities has increased concentrations of greenhouse gases (https://climate.nasa.gov/causes/). Human influence on the climate system is therefore clear, and recent anthropogenic emissions of greenhouse gases are the highest in history. Recent climate changes have had widespread impacts on human and natural systems. Warming of the climate system is unequivocal, and since the 1950s, many of the observed changes are unprecedented over decades to millennia. The atmosphere and ocean have warmed, the amounts of snow and ice have diminished, and sea level has risen ⁸⁰ Climate change is therefore a natural phenomenon that is being amplified by human activities which currently are making it happen in a much faster way. See also: https://www.epa.gov/climatechange/climate-change-basic-information
Marine Impacts of Climate Change	<i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues"	"Rising atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO ₂) is one of the most critical problems because its effects are

⁷⁷ <http://science.sciencemag.org/content/316/5827/987.full>, p. 299

⁷⁸ <http://apps.who.int/medicinedocs/en/d/Jh2996e/6.3.html>

⁷⁹ <http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=360>

⁸⁰ http://www.ipcc.ch/pdf/assessment-report/ar5/syr/AR5_SYR_FINAL_All_Topics.pdf

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	<p><i>IsPartOf:</i> "Climate Change" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>globally pervasive and irreversible on ecological timescales (Natl. Res. Council. 2011). The primary direct consequences are increasing ocean temperatures (Bindoff et al. 2007) and acidity (Doney et al. 2009). Climbing temperatures create a host of additional changes, such as rising sea level, increased ocean stratification, decreased sea-ice extent, and altered patterns of ocean circulation, precipitation, and freshwater input (Figure 1a). In addition, both warming and altered ocean circulation act to reduce subsurface oxygen (O₂) concentrations (Keeling et al. 2010). In recent decades, the rates of change have been rapid and may exceed the current and potential future tolerances of many organisms to adapt. Further, the rates of physical and chemical change in marine ecosystems will almost certainly accelerate over the next several decades in the absence of immediate and dramatic efforts toward climate mitigation (Natl. Res. Council. 2011)." (Source: http://www.annualreviews.org/doi/full/10.1146/annurev-marine-041911-111611)</p>
Blue energy [Renewable Energy (wave, wind, tidal)]	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Blue Growth" <i>Superclass:</i> "Energy"</p>	<p>Ocean energy (EU-definition): "The main forms of ocean energy are waves, tides, marine currents, salinity gradient and temperature gradient. Wave and tidal energy are currently the most mature technologies. Tidal current energy is created by local regular diurnal (24-hour) or semi-diurnal (12+ hour) flows of ocean water caused by the tidal cycle. Kinetic energy can be harnessed, usually nearshore and particularly where there are constrictions, such as straits, islands and passes. Wave energy is created as kinetic energy from the wind is transmitted to the upper surface of the ocean. At present there are several different wave energy technology designs and some are at the cutting edge of engineering design. Ocean thermal energy conversion (OTEC) uses the temperature difference between surface and deep water in a heat cycle to produce electricity. Although tropical areas are most favourable for the exploitation of this source of energy, the potential resources are enormous. Osmotic power generation exploits the energy available from differences in the salt concentration in seawater and is especially suited to countries with abundant fresh water resources flowing into the sea. There are two practical methods for this - reversed electro-dialysis (RED) and pressure retarded osmosis (PRO)".⁸¹ Salinity energy definition: "stored as the salinity difference between seawater and freshwater(...)When a river runs into a sea, spontaneous and irreversible mixing of freshwater and seawater occurs, thereby increasing the entropy of the system. This entropy change can be utilized to convert part of the thermal energy of the fluids into electrical energy [6]." (ref article: http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032113007983)</p>
Maritime, coastal and cruise tourism	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>Concerns:</i> "Tourism" <i>Concerns:</i> "Transportation" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Blue Growth"</p>	<p>Blue Growth study: The extraordinary beauty, cultural wealth and great diversity of EU's coastal areas have made them the preferred destination for many holidaymakers in Europe and abroad, making coastal and maritime tourism an important tourism sector. Employing over 3.2 million people, this sector generates a total of € 183 billion</p>

⁸¹ <https://setis.ec.europa.eu/related-jrc-activities/jrc-setis-reports/ocean-energy-technology-information-sheet>

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	<p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i>"Marine/maritime Spatial Planning" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>in gross value added and representing over one third of the maritime economy. As much as 51% of bed capacity in hotels across Europe is concentrated in regions with a sea border.</p> <p>Coastal and maritime tourism:</p> <p>Coastal tourism refers to land-based tourism activities including swimming, surfing, sunbathing and other coastal recreation activities taking place on the coast for which the proximity to the sea is a condition including also their respective services. Maritime tourism refers to sea-based activities such as boating, yachting, cruising, nautical sports as well as their land-based services (Ecorys, 2013).⁸²</p> <p>B) Cruise tourism is defined as "any maritime-based tour by fare paying guests onboard a vessel whose primary purpose is the accommodation of guests, to visit a variety of destinations rather than to operate a set route".⁸³</p>
Coastal Urbanisation	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>Concerns:</i> "Urbanisation" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Blue Growth" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Supply of labour" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Marine/maritime Spatial Planning" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>"Urbanisation is the increase over time of urban population in proportion to the region's rural population. Urbanisation is studied in terms of its effects on the ecology and economy of a region. The driver also includes the occupation of land by urban land use and related infrastructures."⁸⁴</p>
Fishing and Aquaculture	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Fisheries" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Aquaculture" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Biotechnology" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Marine Biotech" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i>"Blue Growth" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i>"Marine/maritime Spatial Planning" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>Commercial utilization of living being of the oceans and seas by catching or harvesting them with the consequent impact. Commercial fishing definition: "Commercial fishing refers to the harvesting of fish, either in whole or in part, for sale, barter or trade"⁸⁵.</p> <p>Fishing Definitions (extended):</p> <p>"Charter fishing" is defined as "fishing from a vessel carrying a passenger for hire...who is engaged in recreational fishing." The term "commercial fishing" is defined as "fishing in which the fish harvested, either in whole or in part, are intended to enter commerce or enter commerce through sale, barter or trade."</p> <p>"Recreational fishing" means "fishing for sport or pleasure."⁸⁶</p> <p>Definition: "Marine aquaculture refers to the culturing of species that live in the ocean. It implies some form of intervention in the rearing process to enhance production, such as regular stocking, feeding, protection from predators, etc. Farming also implies individual or corporate ownership of the stock being</p>

⁸² http://www.medmaritimeprojects.eu/download/ProjectMediamer/SH_Meeting_WME/WM_Tourism_factsheet_300115.pdf

⁸³ http://www.carib-export.com/obic/documents/Cruise_Market_Study_FINAL.pdf

⁸⁴ http://www.medmaritimeprojects.eu/download/ProjectMediamer/Final_factsheets/AIo_Urbanization_factsheet.pdf

⁸⁵ <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=2990>

⁸⁶ <http://www.nmfs.noaa.gov/sfa/sfaguide/102.htm>

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		cultivated" (FAO definition). (ref: Med-IAMER http://www.medmaritimeprojects.eu/download/ProjectMediamer/Final_factsheets/Alo_Aquaculture_factsheet.pdf)
Ocean Acidification	<i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>Concerns:</i> "Climate Change" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Biogeochemical Cycles" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Marine Pollution" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Ecotax"	"Ocean acidification refers to the process of lowering the oceans' pH (that is, increasing the concentration of hydrogen ions) by dissolving additional carbon dioxide in seawater from the atmosphere. The word "acidification" refers to lowering pH from any starting point to any end point on the pH scale."—James Orr, Senior Scientist, Laboratory for the Sciences of Climate and Environment, France; Christopher L. Sabine, Supervisory Oceanographer, NOAA Pacific Marine Environmental Laboratory, USA; Robert Key, Research Oceanographer, Princeton University, USA. Peer-reviewed, scientific response as part of the EU Epoca project ⁸⁷
Biogeochemical Cycles	<i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>Concerns:</i> "Climate Change"	A biogeochemical cycle is a series of natural processes by which a chemical substance moves through both the biotic (biosphere) and abiotic (lithosphere, atmosphere, and hydrosphere) components of Earth. Several biological, geological and chemical mechanisms are involved to circulate chemical nutrients like carbon, oxygen, nitrogen, phosphorus, calcium, and water etc. In effect, the element is recycled, although in some cycles there may be places (called reservoirs) where the element is accumulated or held for a long period of time (such as an ocean or lake for water). The most well-known and important biogeochemical cycles, for example, include the carbon cycle, the nitrogen cycle, the oxygen cycle, the phosphorus cycle, the sulphur cycle, the water cycle and the rock cycle (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Biogeochemical_cycle).
Coastal Erosion	<i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Climate Change"	"Erosion in the coastal profile. This is taking place in the form of scouring in the foot of the cliffs or in the foot of the dunes. Coast erosion takes place mainly during strong winds, high waves and high tides and storm surge conditions. Coast erosion results in coastline retreat. The rate of erosion is correctly expressed in volume/length/time, e.g. in m ³ /m/year, but erosion rate is often used synonymously with coastline retreat, and thus expressed in m/year." ⁸⁸
Integral cycle of water	<i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Environmental flow" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Grey Water" <i>Concerns:</i> "Water management" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"	The complete water cycle refers to the water cycle that starts with the collection of untreated water, followed by treatment at a treatment plant that results in clean water, maintenance and control of the water tanks, management of distribution networks, and the subsequent distribution to the population. It also includes the collection of the wastewater for post-treatment and release into the rivers and the sea. In the workshop held at nanoGUNE, Spain, on the 13 th of January 2017, following the Structure Democratic Dialogue Process Methodology, the most influential idea that was identified was Management of the Integral cycle of water by professional bodies.
Marine pollution	<i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Grey Water"	"Marine pollution includes a range of threats including from land-based sources, oil spills, untreated sewage, heavy siltation, eutrophication (nutrient enrichment), invasive species, persistent organic

⁸⁷ <http://www.epoca-project.eu/index.php/what-is-ocean-acidification/faq.html>

⁸⁸ K. Mangor 2004: Shoreline Management Guidelines, p. 11

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	<p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Integral cycle of water" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Environmental sustainability" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Deep Sea Mining" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Sea Transportation" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Ecotax"</p>	<p>pollutants (POP's), heavy metals from mine tailings and other sources, acidification, radioactive substances, marine litter, overfishing and destruction of coastal and marine habitats" (McCook 1999, Nyström et al. 2000, Bellwood et al. 2004).⁸⁹ "Marine pollution refers to direct or indirect introduction by humans of substances or energy into the marine environment (including estuaries), resulting in harm to living resources, hazards to human health, hindrances to marine activities including fishing, impairment of the quality of sea water and reduction of amenities".⁹⁰</p>
Monitoring ecosystem	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues"</p>	<p>Monitoring ecosystem consists of following manner;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Determination of biological inventory. • Monitoring of pollution and indicator bacteria in monthly. <p>To create a database based on water quality, pollution and ecological situation by using new technologies</p>
Supply of labour	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues"</p>	<p>Availability of suitable human resources in a particular labor market. http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/labor-supply.html</p>
Marine/maritime Spatial Planning	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Marine Issues" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>Marine spatial planning (MSP) is a process that brings together multiple users of the ocean – including energy, industry, government, conservation and recreation – to make informed and coordinated decisions about how to use marine resources sustainably. MSP generally uses maps to create a more comprehensive picture of a marine area[1] – identifying where and how an ocean area is being used and what natural resources and habitat exist.[2] It is similar to land-use planning, but for marine waters. Through the planning and mapping process of a marine ecosystem, planners can consider the cumulative effect of maritime industries on our seas, seek to make industries more sustainable and proactively minimize conflicts between industries seeking to utilise the same sea area. The intended result of MSP is a more coordinated and sustainable approach to how our oceans are used – ensuring that marine resources and services are utilized, but within clear environmental limits to ensure marine ecosystems remain healthy and biodiversity is conserved. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Marine_spatial_planning)</p>
Seafood safety	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Food security" <i>TheSameAs:</i> "Seafood security" <i>Concerns:</i> "Fisheries" <i>Concerns:</i> "Aquaculture" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>Food safety is a scientific discipline describing handling, preparation, and storage of food in ways that prevent foodborne illness. This includes a number of routines that should be followed to avoid potentially severe health hazards. In this way food safety often overlaps with food defence to prevent harm to consumers. The tracks within this line of thought are safety between industry and the market and then between the market and the consumer. In considering industry to market practices, food safety considerations include the origins of food including the practices relating to food labelling, food hygiene, food additives and pesticide residues, as well as policies on biotechnology and food and guidelines for the management of governmental import and export inspection and certification systems for foods.</p>

⁸⁹ <http://www.grida.no/publications/rr/our-precious-coasts/page/1292.aspx>

⁹⁰ <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=1596>

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		(https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Food_safety)
Maritime-zoning	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Marine/maritime Spatial Planning" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "EU Marine Directives and policies"	Maritime-zoning spatial planning (balance between economic activities and green areas, for biodiversity conservation)
The good city	<i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Marine/maritime Spatial Planning" <i>IsImplementedBy</i> : "Integral cycle of water"	"an expanding habit of solidarity and as a practical but unsettled achievement, constantly building on experiments through which difference and multiplicity can be mobilised for common gain and against harm and want" ⁹¹ .
Grey water	<i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "Ecotax"	Grey water (also spelled graywater, greywater, gray water) or sullage is all wastewater generated in households or office buildings from streams without fecal contamination, i.e. all streams except for the wastewater from toilets. Sources of grey water include, e.g. sinks, showers, baths, clothes washing machines or dish washers. As grey water contains fewer pathogens than domestic wastewater, it is generally safer to handle and easier to treat and reuse onsite for toilet flushing, landscape or crop irrigation, and other non-potable uses. The application of grey water reuse in urban water systems provides substantial benefits for both the water supply subsystem by reducing the demand for fresh clean water as well as the wastewater subsystems by reducing the amount of wastewater required to be conveyed and treated. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Greywater)
Ecotax	<i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "EU Marine Directives and policies" <i>Concerns</i> : "Public policy" <i>Concerns</i> : "Bioeconomy"	An Ecotax (short for ecological taxation) is a tax levied on activities which are considered to be harmful to the environment and is intended to promote environmentally friendly activities via economic incentives. Such a policy can complement or avert the need for regulatory (command and control) approaches. Often, an ecotax policy proposal may attempt to maintain overall tax revenue by proportionately reducing other taxes (e.g. taxes on human labour and renewable resources); such proposals are known as a green tax shift towards ecological taxation (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ecotax). Environmental challenges are increasing the pressure on governments to find ways to reduce environmental damage while minimising harm to economic growth. Governments have a range of tools at their disposal, including regulations, information programmes, innovation policies, environmental subsidies and environmental taxes. Environmental taxes have many important advantages, such as environmental effectiveness, economic efficiency, the ability to raise public revenue, and transparency. Also, environmental taxes have been successfully used to address a wide range of issues including waste disposal, water pollution and air emissions. Environmental pricing through taxation leaves consumers and businesses the flexibility to determine how best to reduce their environmental footprint ⁹² .
Environmental flow	<i>IsInfluencedBy</i> : "EU Marine Directives and policies" <i>Concerns</i> : "Integral cycle of water"	Environmental flows describe the quantity, timing, and quality of water flows required to sustain freshwater and estuarine ecosystems and the human livelihoods and well being that depend on these

⁹¹ Ash Amin 2006: The Good City. Urban studies, Vol. 43, nos 5/6

⁹² <https://www.oecd.org/env/tools-evaluation/48164926.pdf>

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		<p>ecosystems. Through implementation of environmental flows, water managers strive to achieve a flow regime, or pattern, that provides for human uses and maintains the essential processes required to support healthy river ecosystems. Environmental flows do not necessarily require restoring the natural, pristine flow patterns that would occur absent human development, use, and diversion but, instead, are intended to produce a broader set of values and benefits from rivers than from management focused strictly on water supply, energy, recreation, or flood control.</p> <p>Rivers are parts of integrated systems that include floodplains and riparian corridors. Collectively these systems provide a large suite of benefits. However, the world's rivers are increasingly being altered through the construction of dams, diversions, and levees. More than half of the world's large rivers are dammed, a figure that continues to increase. Almost 1,000 dams are planned or under construction in South America and 50 new dams are planned on China's Yangtze River alone. Dams and other river structures change the downstream flow patterns and consequently affect water quality, temperature, sediment movement and deposition, fish and wildlife, and the livelihoods of people who depend on healthy river ecosystems. Environmental flows seek to maintain these river functions while at the same time providing for traditional offstream benefits.</p> <p>(https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Environmental_flow)</p>
<p>Growth sectors: major growing sectors derived and adjusted by the EU Blue Growth Strategy</p>		
<p>Sectors (Blue Growth and supplementary sectors)</p>		<p>The Blue Growth strategy highlights five sectors as drivers: aquaculture, marine renewable energy, marine mineral mining, marine biotechnology, and marine and coastal tourism. However, in order to highlight and be able to include additional growth- and innovation opportunities, based on RRI, the MARINA consortium has supplemented with several sectors</p>
<p>Fisheries</p>	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Aquaculture" <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Seafood safety" <i>Concerns:</i> "Jobs and Investments" <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Tourism" <i>Concerns:</i> "Fishing and aquaculture" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>Commercial fishing refers to the harvesting of fish, either in whole or in part, for sale, barter or trade⁹³.</p>
<p>Aquaculture</p>	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors" <i>Overlaps:</i> "Fisheries"</p>	<p>Marine aquaculture refers to the culturing of species that live in the ocean. It implies some form of intervention in the rearing process to enhance production, such as regular stocking, feeding, protection</p>

⁹³ <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=2990>

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	<p><i>IsFosteredBy</i>: "Seafood safety" <i>Concerns</i> : "Jobs and Investments" <i>Concerns</i> : "Fishing and aquaculture" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>from predators, etc. Farming also implies individual or corporate ownership of the stock being cultivated (FAO definition). Med-IAMER (http://www.medmaritimeprojects.eu/download/ProjectMediamer/Final_factsheets/Alo_Aquaculture_factsheet.pdf) , considers marine aquaculture that takes place in the ocean (that is, in cages, on the seafloor, or suspended in the water column).</p>
Tourism	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Sectors" <i>IsFosteredBy</i>: "Transport" <i>Concerns</i> : "Jobs and Investments" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "EU Marine Directives and policies" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Ecotax"</p>	<p>Tourism is defined as the activities of persons travelling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes not related to the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited⁹⁴.</p>
Transport	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Sectors" <i>Concerns</i> : "Jobs and Investments" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "EU Marine Directives and policies" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Ecotax"</p>	<p>Any movement of goods and/or passengers using rail/road/maritime shipping/ air⁹⁵</p>
Energy	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Sectors" <i>Concerns</i> : "Jobs and Investments" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "EU Marine Directives and policies" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Ecotax"</p>	<p>The sector dealing with the production, sale and consumption of energy such as natural gas, nuclear power, non-renewable waste, renewables, solid fuels, crude oil and petroleum products⁹⁶</p>
Ports, harbours and marinas	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Sectors" <i>IsFosteredBy</i>: "Tourism" <i>Concerns</i> : "Jobs and Investments" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>The sector dealing with the development of the coastal areas by providing services for ships, including: Port: "Place having facilities for merchant ships to moor and to load or discharge goods or passengers to or from seagoing vessels⁹⁷ . Harbour: "A place on the coast where ships may moor in shelter, especially one protected from rough water by piers, jetties, and other artificial structures"⁹⁸</p>

⁹⁴ <http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=2725>

⁹⁵ The definition is a synthesis of OECD STATISTICAL TERMS (<http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/search.asp>) combined with the four subsectors of the EU transport policy (https://europa.eu/european-union/topics/transport_en)

⁹⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/2014_energy_market_en.pdf

⁹⁷ <http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=4231>

⁹⁸ <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/harbour>

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		Marina: "A specially designed harbour with moorings for pleasure yachts and small boats" ⁹⁹
Minerals and Metals	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Deep Sea Mining"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Jobs and Investments"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	Minerals are solid, naturally occurring inorganic substances that can be found in the earth's crust. They are formed without the intervention of humans and have a definite chemical composition and crystal structure. Metals are elementary substances, such as gold, silver and copper that are crystalline when solid and naturally occurring in minerals. They often have the characteristics of being good conductors of electricity and heat, of being shiny in appearance and of being malleable. The metals we see day-to-day are produced through the conversion of metallic ores to a final form. This, in the majority of cases, requires the use of chemicals and special technologies. ¹⁰⁰
Oil and gas	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Deep Sea Mining"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Jobs and Investments"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	Conventional oil and gas refers to petroleum, or crude oil, and raw natural gas extracted from the ground by conventional means and methods.
Waste Management	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Urbanisation"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Urban and industrial uses"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Maritime, coastal and cruise tourism"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Jobs and Investments"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Resilience"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Marine Litter"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Eutrophication"</p> <p><i>Overlaps:</i> "Coastal Cities"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	Waste Management concerns the collection, transportation, and disposal of garbage, sewage, and other waste products. Waste management encompasses management of all processes and resources for proper handling of waste materials, from maintenance of waste transport trucks and dumping facilities to compliance with health codes and environmental regulations. ¹⁰¹
Agriculture	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Jobs and Investments"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Climate Change"</p>	The science or practice of farming, including cultivation of the soil for the growing of crops and the rearing of animals to provide food, wool, and other products. ¹⁰²

⁹⁹ <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/marina>

¹⁰⁰ <https://www.icmm.com/en-gb/metals-and-minerals/producing-metals/what-are-minerals-metals->

¹⁰¹ <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/waste-management.html>

¹⁰² <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/agriculture>

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Forestry	<i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors" <i>Concerns:</i> "Jobs and Investments" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Climate Change"	The science or practice of planting, managing, and caring for forests. ¹⁰³
Urban and industrial uses	<i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"	Water reuse can contribute to meeting a number of water needs for the environment and different business sectors, among which there are: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • industrial uses: such as cooling water, process water, aggregate washing, concrete making, soil compaction, dust control. • Urban/landscape uses, such as irrigation of public parks, recreational and sporting facilities, private gardens, road sides, street cleaning, fire protection systems, vehicle washing, toilet flushing, dust control.¹⁰⁴
Security/defence	<i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"	The European Commission's defence industrial policy is designed to promote competition, innovation, support small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and provide a strong industrial base for the EU's Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP). ¹⁰⁵ Security: "The state of being free from danger or threat." ¹⁰⁶ Defence: "The action of defending from or resisting attack" ¹⁰⁷
Education and research	<i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"	Education and research are central components of the blue growth strategy and it is recognized that training itself, and the delivery of high-quality graduate programmes, is part of the engine which drives innovation and technology development in maritime sectors. A strong vision for the future of marine science education and training must identify ways to improve the capabilities of the next generation of marine scientists and engineers to work at a systems level, applying multi-disciplinary knowledge to address complex marine issues which cut across scientific, environmental and social systems. To achieve this, it is necessary to examine the very complex educational landscape that currently produces our professional marine experts, identify some of the key issues and challenges faced by educators, and make recommendations on how to improve marine higher educational training in Europe. ¹⁰⁸

¹⁰³ <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/forestry>

¹⁰⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/pdf/Guidelines_on_water_reuse.pdf

¹⁰⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/growth/sectors/defence/industrial-policy_en

¹⁰⁶ <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/security>

¹⁰⁷ <https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/defence>

¹⁰⁸ <http://www.marineboard.eu/marine-graduate-training>

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Urbanisation	<i>Superclass:</i> "Sectors" <i>Concerns:</i> "Coastal Cities" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"	Urbanisation is an increase in a population in cities and towns versus rural areas. Urbanization began during the industrial revolution, when workers moved towards manufacturing hubs in cities to obtain jobs in factories as agricultural jobs became less common. ¹⁰⁹
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Themes: major multidimensional themes debated at international level partly derived from the European Environmental Agency's website

Themes		These themes are derived partly from the European Environmental Agency's website ('Maritime activities and the marine environment') as well as from themes described in a subsequent indicator section ¹¹⁰
Marine Protected Areas	<i>Superclass:</i> "Themes" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Marine and maritime research" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Inland water research"	"MPAs are geographically distinct zones for which conservation objectives can be set. They are often established in an attempt to strike a balance between ecological constraints and economic activity, so that the seas may continue to allow for goods and services to be delivered. Marine reserves are MPAs where human impact is kept to a minimum, e.g. extraction is not permitted. MPA networks are a collection of individual MPAs or reserves operating synergistically, at various spatial scales, and covering a range of protection levels, designed to meet objectives that individual MPAs cannot achieve. It should be noted that many diverse definitions of MPAs exist". ¹¹¹
Water management (physical restructuring of rivers, coastline or seabed)	<i>Superclass:</i> "Themes" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Marine and maritime research" <i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Inland water research"	Integrated Water Resource Management can be defined as follows: 'IWRM is a process which promotes the co-ordinated development and management of water, land and related resources, in order to maximize the resultant economic and social welfare in an equitable manner without compromising the sustainability of vital ecosystems" ¹¹² .
Biodiversity	<i>Superclass:</i> "Themes" <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Marine Protected Areas" <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Sustainable agriculture and forestry" <i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Marine and maritime research"	Biodiversity refers to the range of genetic differences, species differences and ecosystem differences in a given area ¹¹³ . Biological diversity, or biodiversity, describes the variety of life on earth, and this diversity operates at various scales, from genes, species to entire ecosystems. Biodiversity therefore refers to all life-forms and

¹⁰⁹ <http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/urbanization.html>

¹¹⁰ <http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/environmental-indicator-report-2012/environmental-indicator-report-2012-ecosystem/part2.xhtml>, accessed March 15 2017

¹¹¹ <http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/marine-protected-areas-in-europes>

¹¹² <http://www.un.org/waterforlifedecade/iwrm.shtml>

¹¹³ <http://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=204>

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	<p><i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Climate action" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Environment" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Urbanisation" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Agriculture" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Forestry" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Climate Change" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>their behaviours, the environments or habitats in which they live, and the complex system of relationships between organisms, such as food webs and competition for resources.¹¹⁴</p>
Resilience	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Themes" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Water management" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Coastal protection" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Inclusive societies" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Innovative societies" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Reflective societies" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Infrastructure protection" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Security" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Digital security" <i>IsFosteredBy</i> "Biodiversity" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Climate Change" <i>Concerns</i>: "Coastal hazards, vulnerability and risk" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>Resilience can be defined as the degree to which an ecosystem or a part/component of it is able to recover from disturbance without major persistent change (http://www.coastalwiki.org/wiki/Resilience).</p>
Non indigenous species	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Themes" <i>Concerns</i>: "Biodiversity" <i>Concerns</i>: "Environment" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) defines non-indigenous species as species whose introduction or spread threaten biodiversity. Non-indigenous species are species introduced outside their natural past or present range, which might survive and subsequently reproduce. These species are introduced in situations where exchange of people or goods takes place between countries and continents, by shipping for example.</p>
Coastal hazards, vulnerability and risk	<p><i>Superclass</i>: "Themes" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Coastal protection" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Resilience" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Marine and maritime research" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Inland water research" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "Climate Change" <i>IsInfluencedBy</i>: "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>Coastal Hazards are natural physical phenomena that expose a coastal area to risk of property damage, loss of life and environmental degradation. Examples include storms accompanied with strong winds, high waves and storm surges. Tsunamis, coastal erosion and overwash/overtopping are also examples of coastal hazards. Some biologic phenomenon can also be seen as coastal hazards. A good example would be harmful algae blooms which can cause severe ecological, health and economic impacts. Within coastal zone management, vulnerability expresses the likelihood of a given part of the coast, habitat, community, ecosystem or infrastructure to be affected by coastal hazards. Vulnerability excludes the</p>

¹¹⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/marine/good-environmental-status/descriptor-1/index_en.htm

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		<p>human factor and relates only to the natural ability to be protected from hazards.</p> <p>Risk includes the human factor and is the result of the likelihood of occurrence of a specific coastal hazard event multiplied by the socio-economic damage caused by that event.</p> <p>An example would be the fact that a coastal stretch with low lying and breached dunes is highly vulnerable to the overwash hazard but if there is no human occupation the risk level is minimum or inexistent. A major storm would cause no direct threat to human occupation on that beach. On the contrary, a densely occupied area fronted with continuous robust high dunes could nevertheless correspond to a high risk situation since a major storm could impose serious damage on property and life.</p> <p>(See http://www.coastalwiki.org/wiki/Risk_and_coastal_zone_policy:_example_from_the_Netherlands.)</p>
Overwash and overtopping	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Themes "</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Climate Change"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Coastal hazards, vulnerability and risk"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Environment"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Inland water research"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Coastal protection"</p>	<p>Overwash occurs when the flow of water of a breaking wave runs up the beach and overcomes the frontal dune. It normally transports sediment from the low-lying section of the beach to the dunes or to the environment inward. Apart from flooding and destruction, overwash can therefore contribute to significant imbalances in the coastal sedimentary equilibrium and cause important morphological changes along the coast. Overwash occurs mostly during periods when high energy waves, storm surge and high tides coincide. Overwash is one of the dominant mechanisms involved in barrier-islands landwards migration since they can transfer large amounts of sediment from the sea-facing flank of the barrier to its lagoon side, making the position of the barrier to be displaced landwards.</p> <p>Overtopping occurs when the flow of water of a breaking wave runs up a coastal engineering structure like a port jetty, an oceanfront revetment or any type of hard coastal defence. Overtopping is therefore a serious threat to coastal engineering structures and to the property (ships, goods, equipment, buildings, vehicles) they protect as well to the life of those who live or work nearby.</p>
Coastal protection	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Themes "</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Coastal hazards, vulnerability and risk"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Overwash and overtopping"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Inland water research"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Marine and maritime research"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Inland water research"</p>	<p>Coastal protection refers to the measures aimed at protecting the coast mostly against shoreline retreat, overwash and coastal flooding. It aims at protecting housing, infrastructure, the coast and the hinterland from erosion and storm impacts often at the expense of losing the beach and the dynamic coastal landscape (http://www.coastalwiki.org/wiki/Coast_protection).</p> <p>Hard coastal protection includes all the engineering works based on using traditional materials like rocks, cement, iron and wood to hold the shoreline in a given position, to promote sediment accretion along beaches, to increase the height of longshore structures that protect coastal human occupied areas or to stabilize coastal cliffs. Examples are seawalls, revetments, breakwaters, bulkheads and groins. The efficiency of these actions are usually restricted to the nearby updrift areas where sediment gets trapped. The downdrift areas tend to start being impacted by the same problem, sediment starvation, meaning the problem was not solved; it was merely transferred to a new spot. Hard engineering works are seen as permanent solutions but the natural wearing cause by waves forces the need to keep a high-cost maintenance.</p>

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		Soft coastal protection encompasses actions that reduce the vulnerability of the coast by promoting natural dynamic processes. These include artificial beach nourishment, sand fences that lead to wind borne sand deposition and dune development, plantation of natural dune vegetation. These actions are many times implemented together and tend to have little negative impacts on the coast. Due to their dynamic character they should never be seen as permanent. They should therefore be planned within a long-term coastal protection strategy that foresees their periodic repetition.
Marine litter	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Themes"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Waste management"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	Marine litter consists of items that have been deliberately discarded, unintentionally lost, or transported by winds and rivers, into the sea and on beaches. It mainly consists of plastics, wood, metals, glass, rubber, clothing and paper. Land-based sources account for up to 80% of marine litter – these include tourism, sewage and illegal or poorly managed landfills. The main sea-based sources are shipping and fishing. ¹¹⁵
Eutrophication	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Themes"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Agriculture"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Urbanisation"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Water management"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	Eutrophication is a process driven by the enrichment of water by nutrients, especially compounds of nitrogen and/or phosphorus, leading to: increased growth, primary production and biomass of algae; changes in the balance of organisms; and water quality degradation. The consequences of eutrophication are undesirable if they appreciably degrade ecosystem health and biodiversity and/or the sustainable provision of goods and services. ¹¹⁶
Coastal Cities	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Themes"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Inland water research"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Smart cities"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Fast Track Innovation in Transport"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Resource efficiency"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Raw materials"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Low carbon technologies"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Energy efficiency"</p> <p><i>IsFosteredBy:</i> "Green Vehicles"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Urbanisation"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Marine and maritime research"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Waste management"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Mobility"</p>	Throughout history, people have settled on coasts to take advantage of the amenities the oceans offer – a food supply, a source of transport, a defensible position and a healthy location. However, as coastal cities grow, they become detached from their environmental surroundings, while still requiring services from their local ecosystem. The demands placed on the host ecosystem threaten the viability of the cities themselves. Today, it is estimated that almost 50 per cent of the world's coasts are threatened by development-related activities. Municipal, industrial and agricultural wastes and run-off, as well as atmospheric deposition, affect the most productive areas of the marine environment, including estuaries and near-shore coastal waters. Physical alterations to the coastal zone also threaten the marine environment. (http://www.coastalwiki.org/wiki/Coastal_Cities)

¹¹⁵ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/marine/pdf/flyer_marine_litter.pdf

¹¹⁶ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/marine/good-environmental-status/descriptor-5/index_en.htm

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Technology and Innovation	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Themes"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Jobs and Investments"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Trade and Supply Chains"</p> <p><i>IsImplementedBy:</i> "Education and research"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>The pace of technological change, particularly in the fields of information, communication, nano- and biotechnologies, is unprecedented. This provides opportunities to reduce humanity's impact on the environment and reliance on non-renewable natural resources, while improving lifestyles, stimulating innovation and green growth. The risks and uncertainties associated with technological innovation can be managed using regulatory frameworks and the precautionary principle. By recalibrating its institutions, policies and environmental knowledge base, Europe can support better risk management, while enhancing innovation and the diffusion of new technologies.¹¹⁷</p>
Trade and Supply Chains	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Themes"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Jobs and Investments"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>Trade: "Commercial transaction involving the sale and purchase of a good, service, or information". (http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/trade.html)</p> <p>Supply Chains: "Entire network of entities, directly or indirectly interlinked and interdependent in serving the same consumer or customer. It comprises of vendors that supply raw material, producers who convert the material into products, warehouses that store, distribution centers that deliver to the retailers, and retailers who bring the product to the ultimate user. Supply chains underlie value-chains because, without them, no producer has the ability to give customers what they want, when and where they want, at the price they want. Producers compete with each other only through their supply chains, and no degree of improvement at the producer's end can make up for the deficiencies in a supply chain which reduce the producer's ability to compete." (http://www.businessdictionary.com/definition/supply-chain.html)</p>
Jobs and Investments	<p><i>Superclass:</i> "Themes"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "Bioeconomy"</p> <p><i>Concerns:</i> "Fishing and aquaculture"</p> <p><i>IsInfluencedBy:</i> "EU Marine Directives and policies"</p>	<p>One of the priorities of the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund is to increase employment, territorial cohesion and social inclusion in fisheries dependent communities. The diversification of local economies, in particular towards other sectors of the maritime economy, will create new jobs, investments, and growth opportunities in coastal areas.¹¹⁸</p>

Policy Framework: a logical structure for organizing policy documentation to be used in the planning and development of the policies for an organization.

¹¹⁷ <http://www.eea.europa.eu/soer-2015/global/technology>

¹¹⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/budget/library/biblio/documents/2016/DB/DB2016_WDIB_en.pdf

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Policy Framework		A logical structure for organizing policy documentation to be used in the planning and development of the policies for an organization.
Directives and policies	<i>Superclass: "Policy Framework"</i>	Directives and policies define principles, rules, guidelines and the basic procedures to be followed in the development of an activity
EU Marine Directives and policies	<i>Superclass: "Directives and policies"</i>	Directives effective in EU member states and dealing directly with the marine waters
Fish Water Directive – 2006/44/EC (FWD)	<i>InstanceOf: " EU Marine Directives and policies "</i>	Directive 2006/44/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 September 2006 on the quality of fresh waters needing protection or improvement in order to support fish life
Shellfish Water Directive – 2006/113/EC (SWD)	<i>InstanceOf: " EU Marine Directives and policies "</i>	Directive 2006/113/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on the quality required of shellfish waters
Bathing Water Directive – 2006/7/EC (BWD)	<i>InstanceOf: " EU Marine Directives and policies "</i>	Directive 2006/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 February 2006 concerning the management of bathing water quality and repealing Directive 76/160/EEC
Water Framework Directive (EC, 2000)	<i>InstanceOf: " EU Marine Directives and policies "</i>	Directive 2000/60/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2000 establishing a framework for Community action in the field of water policy
Marine Strategy Framework Directive – 2008/56/EC (MSF)	<i>InstanceOf: " EU Marine Directives and policies "</i>	Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive)
Birds Directive 2009/147/EEC	<i>InstanceOf: " EU Marine Directives and policies "</i>	Directive 2009/147/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 November 2009 on the conservation of wild birds
Habitats Directive 92/43/EEC	<i>InstanceOf: " EU Marine Directives and policies "</i>	Adopted in 1992, the Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora aims to promote the maintenance of biodiversity, taking account of economic, social, cultural and regional requirements.
Common Fishery Policy (REGULATION (EU) No 1380/2013)	<i>InstanceOf: " EU Marine Directives and policies "</i>	Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 on the Common Fisheries Policy, amending Council Regulations (EC) No 1954/2003 and (EC) No 1224/2009 and repealing Council Regulations (EC) No 2371/2002 and (EC) No 639/2004 and Council Decision 2004/585/EC
Maritime Spatial planning (EC, 2014)	<i>InstanceOf: " EU Marine Directives and policies "</i>	Directive 2014/89/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 July 2014 establishing a framework for maritime spatial planning

EU Marine Regions: acknowledged marine areas in the EU¹¹⁹ on the basis of geographical and environmental criteria

EU Marine Region		European marine regions and sub-regions on the basis of geographical and environmental criteria
Baltic Sea	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Sea of the Atlantic Ocean, enclosed by Scandinavia, Finland, the Baltic countries, and the North European Plain. It includes the Gulf of Bothnia, the Bay of Bothnia, the Gulf of Finland, the Gulf of Riga, and the Bay of

¹¹⁹The EEA provides the following overview, the Greenland Sea not included: http://www.eea.europa.eu/about-us/countries-and-eionet/marine-regions/marine-regions-map/image_large

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		Gdańsk
Black Sea	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Sea between Eastern Europe and Western Asia, bounded by Bulgaria, Georgia, Romania, Russia, Turkey, and Ukraine.
Barents Sea	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Sea of the Arctic Ocean,[1] located off the northern coasts of Norway and Russia divided between Norwegian and Russian territorial waters
Bay of Biscay and Iberian	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Gulf of the northeast Atlantic Ocean located south of the Celtic Sea
Celtic Sea	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Area of the Atlantic Ocean off the south coast of Ireland bounded to the east by Saint George's Channel;[1] other limits include the Bristol Channel, the English Channel, and the Bay of Biscay, as well as adjacent portions of Wales, Cornwall, Devon, and Brittany.
Greater North Sea including Kattegat and English Channel	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Sea of the Atlantic Ocean located between Great Britain, Scandinavia, Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium, and France.
Greenland Sea	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Sea that borders Greenland to the west, the Svalbard archipelago to the east, Fram Strait and the Arctic Ocean to the north, and the Norwegian Sea and Iceland to the south.
Iceland Sea	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Sea in the North Atlantic Ocean
Mediterranean Sea	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Sea connected to the Atlantic Ocean, surrounded by the Mediterranean Basin and almost completely enclosed by land: on the north by Southern Europe and Anatolia, on the south by North Africa, and on the east by the Levant.
Sea North-East	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Sea of the Atlantic Ocean located between Great Britain, Scandinavia, Germany, the Netherlands, Belgium, and France.
Norwegian Sea	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Sea in the North Atlantic Ocean, northwest of Norway. It is located between the North Sea (i.e. north of the United Kingdom) and the Greenland Sea and adjoins the North Atlantic Ocean to the west and the Barents Sea to the northeast. In the southwest, it is separated from the Atlantic Ocean by a submarine ridge running between Iceland and the Faroe Islands. To the North, the Jan Mayen Ridge separates it from the Greenland Sea.
Macaronesia Sea	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Region of the North Atlantic Ocean surrounding the Azores (Portugal), Madeira (Portugal) and Canary (Spain) archipelagos.
Atlantic Ocean	<i>InstanceOf: "EU Marine Region"</i>	Sea extended longitudinally between Eurasia and Africa to the east, and the Americas to the west.

States: autonomous political structure and government

States		A state is a type of polity that is an organized political community living under a single system of government. States may or may not be sovereign. For instance, federated states are members of a federal union, and may have only partial sovereignty, but are, nonetheless, states. Some states are subject to external sovereignty or hegemony, in which ultimate sovereignty lies in another state. States that are
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		sovereign are known as sovereign states. (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/State_(polity))
EU member states	<i>Superclass: "States"</i>	27 European member states
Austria	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Federal republic and a landlocked country of over 8.7 million people in Central Europe.
Belgium	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Sovereign state in Western Europe bordered by France, the Netherlands, Germany, Luxembourg, and the North Sea.
Bulgaria	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Country in south-eastern Europe bordered by Romania to the north, Serbia and Macedonia to the west, Greece and Turkey to the south, and the Black Sea to the east.
Croatia	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Sovereign state between Central Europe, Southeast Europe, and the Mediterranean.
Cyprus	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Island country in the Eastern Mediterranean and the third largest and third most populous island in the Mediterranean. It is located south of Turkey, west of Syria and Lebanon, northwest of Israel and Palestine, north of Egypt, and southeast of Greece.
Czech Republic	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Nation state in Central Europe bordered by Germany to the west, Austria to the south, Slovakia to the east and Poland to the northeast.
Denmark	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	A Scandinavian country in Europe. The southernmost and smallest of the Nordic countries, it is south-west of Sweden and south of Norway, and bordered to the south by Germany.
Estonia	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Country in the Baltic region of Northern Europe. It is bordered to the north by the Gulf of Finland, to the west by the Baltic Sea, to the south by Latvia (343 km), and to the east by Lake Peipus and Russia.
Finland	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Sovereign state in Northern Europe. A peninsula with the Gulf of Finland to the south and the Gulf of Bothnia to the west, the country has land borders with Sweden to the northwest, Norway to the north, and Russia to the east. Estonia is south of the country across the Gulf of Finland.
France	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Territory in western Europe and several overseas regions and territories.[XVI] The European, or metropolitan, area of France extends from the Mediterranean Sea to the English Channel and the North Sea, and from the Rhine to the Atlantic Ocean. Overseas France include French Guiana on the South American continent and several island territories in the Atlantic, Pacific and Indian oceans.
Germany	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Federal parliamentary republic in central-western Europe. It includes 16 constituent states, covers an area of 357,021 square kilometres (137,847 sq mi).
Greece	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Country in south-eastern Europe. Situated on the southern tip of the Balkan peninsula, it shares land borders with Albania to the northwest, the Republic of Macedonia and Bulgaria to the north, and Turkey to the northeast. Greece consists of nine geographic regions: Macedonia, Central Greece, the Peloponnese, Thessaly, Epirus, the Aegean Islands (including the Dodecanese and Cyclades), Thrace, Crete, and the Ionian Islands.
Hungary	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states"</i>	Unitary parliamentary republic in Central Europe. It covers an area of 93,030 square kilometres (35,920 sq mi), situated in the Carpathian Basin and bordered by Slovakia to the north, Romania to the east, Serbia to the south, Croatia to the southwest, Slovenia to the west, Austria to the northwest, and Ukraine to the northeast.

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Ireland	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Sovereign state in north-western Europe occupying about five-sixths of the island of Ireland. The state shares its only land border with Northern Ireland, a part of the United Kingdom. It is otherwise surrounded by the Atlantic Ocean, with the Celtic Sea to the south, Saint George's Channel to the south-east, and the Irish Sea to the east.
Italy	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Unitary parliamentary republic in Europe. Located in the heart of the Mediterranean Sea, Italy shares open land borders with France, Switzerland, Austria, Slovenia, San Marino and Vatican City.
Latvia	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Country in the Baltic region of Northern Europe, one of the three Baltic states. It is bordered by Estonia to the north, Lithuania to the south, Russia to the east, and Belarus to the southeast, as well as a maritime border to the west alongside Sweden.
Lithuania	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Country in Northern Europe. One of the three Baltic states, it is situated along the south-eastern shore of the Baltic Sea, to the east of Sweden and Denmark. It is bordered by Latvia to the north, Belarus to the east and south, Poland to the south, and Kaliningrad Oblast (a Russian exclave) to the southwest.
Luxembourg	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Landlocked country in western Europe. It is bordered by Belgium to the west and north, Germany to the east, and France to the south.
Malta	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Southern European island country consisting of an archipelago in the Mediterranean Sea. It lies 80 km (50 mi) south of Italy, 284 km (176 mi) east of Tunisia,[8] and 333 km (207 mi) north of Libya.
Netherlands	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	A densely populated country located in Western Europe with three island territories in the Caribbean. The European part of the Netherlands borders Germany to the east, Belgium to the south, and the North Sea to the northwest, sharing maritime borders with Belgium, the United Kingdom, and Germany.
Poland	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Country in Central Europe, situated between the Baltic Sea in the north and two mountain ranges (the Sudetes and Carpathian Mountains) in the south. Bordered by Germany to the west; the Czech Republic and Slovakia to the south; Ukraine and Belarus to the east; and the Baltic Sea, Kaliningrad Oblast (a Russian exclave) and Lithuania to the north.
Portugal	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Country on the Iberian Peninsula, in South-western Europe. It is the westernmost country of mainland Europe. To the west and south it is bordered by the Atlantic Ocean and to the east and north by Spain.
Romania	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Sovereign state located in South-eastern Europe. It borders the Black Sea, Bulgaria, Ukraine, Hungary, Serbia, and Moldova.
Slovakia	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Landlocked country in Central Europe. It is bordered by the Czech Republic and Austria to the west, Poland to the north, Ukraine to the east and Hungary to the south.
Slovenia	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Nation state in southern Central Europe, located at the crossroads of main European cultural and trade routes. It is bordered by Italy to the west, Austria to the north, Hungary to the northeast, Croatia to the south and southeast, and the Adriatic Sea to the southwest.
Spain	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Sovereign state largely located on the Iberian Peninsula in south-western Europe, with two large archipelagos, the Balearic Islands in the Mediterranean Sea and the Canary Islands off the North African Atlantic coast, two cities Ceuta and Melilla in the North African mainland and several small islands in the Alboran Sea near the Moroccan coast.

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Sweden	<i>InstanceOf: "EU member states "</i>	Scandinavian country in Northern Europe. It borders Norway to the west and Finland to the east, and is connected to Denmark in the southwest by a bridge-tunnel across the Öresund.
Non-EU member states	<i>Superclass: "States "</i>	Non-EU member states are European countries that participate in the single market but not in the customs union.
United Kingdom	<i>InstanceOf: " Non-EU member states "</i>	The United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland, commonly known as the United Kingdom (UK) or Britain, is a sovereign country in western Europe.
Turkey	<i>InstanceOf: " Non-EU member states "</i>	Turkey, officially the Republic of Turkey is a transcontinental country in Eurasia, mainly in Anatolia in Western Asia, with a smaller portion on the Balkan peninsula in Southeast Europe.

5. Conclusion

Deliverable D2.3 is contributing in defining relevant concepts and their relationships in the domains of interest of the MARINA project. The next steps are:

- to refine and complete the concept definition and their relationships with inputs from Deliverable D3.3
- to formalise and implement the ontology in RDF using the Wikimedia framework (Task 4.2)
- to test the ontology in the wiki pages and in the MARINA WKSP platform (Task 4.2)